

AMERICAN JOURNAL
OF NUMISMATICS

29

Second Series, continuing
The American Numismatic Society Museum Notes

THE AMERICAN NUMISMATIC SOCIETY
NEW YORK
2017

© 2018 The American Numismatic Society

ISSN: 1053-8356
ISBN 978-0-89722-348-5

Printed in China

CONTENTS

Editorial Committee	v
NATHANIEL J. ANDRADE. The Silver Coinage of Syrian Manbog (Hierapolis-Bambyke)	1
LLOYD W. H. TAYLOR. The Damaskos Mint of Alexander the Great	47
D. ALEX WALTHALL. Numismatic Material from Late Third-Century Contexts at Morgantina (Sicily)	101
JANE SANCINITO. The Antiochene Coinage of Trajan Decius (249–251 CE)	159
PETER BARTLETT, DAVID YOON, AND RUTH PLIEGO. Weight, Fineness, and Debasement in Visigothic <i>Tremisses</i> from Theudis to Leovigild: New Evidence from the Hoards of Seville and Reccopolis	149
ANWER AHMEDZHANOV. Hedlinger’s Rouble	213
PHILLIP B. WAGONER AND PANKAJ TANDON. The Bahmani “Currency Reform” of the Early Fifteenth Century in Light of the Akola Hoard	227
MICHAEL ZACHARY. The General Issue Ten-Cash Coins of the Republic of China: Noteworthy Examples in the ANS Collection	269

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF NUMISMATICS

Ute Wartenberg
David Yoon
Editors

Oliver D. Hoover
Managing Editor

Editorial Committee

John W. Adams
Boston, Massachusetts

Paul T. Keyser
Google

Jere L. Bacharach
University of Washington

John M. Kleeberg
New York, New York

Gilles Bransbourg
American Numismatic Society

John H. Kroll
Oxford, England

Andrew Burnett
British Museum

Ira Rezak
Stony Brook, New York

Wolfgang Fischer-Bossert
Austrian Academy of Science

Stuart D. Sears
Westport, Massachusetts

Evridiki Georganteli
Harvard University

Peter van Alfen
American Numismatic Society

Kenneth W. Harl
Tulane University

Bernhard Weisser
Münzkabinett

Jonathan Kagan
New York, New York

Staatliche Museen zu Berlin

Weight, Fineness, and Debasement in Visigothic *Tremisses* from Theudis to Leovigild: New Evidence from the Hoards of Seville and Reccopolis

PLATES 27–30

PETER BARTLETT*, DAVID YOON,** AND RUTH PLIEGO***

Prior research has indicated a significant reduction in weight for pre-regal Visigothic *tremisses* around the 570s, toward the end of the series. Limited studies have suggested a similar reduction in fineness around that time. This article presents measurements of specific gravity for two hoards of pre-regal *tremisses* from Spain, that of Calle Cuna in Seville, dated to the years around 550, and that of Zorita de los Canes, site of the Visigothic city of Reccopolis, dated to around 578. This additional metrological evidence shows a more complex sequence of changes in standard, with significant debasement happening during the third quarter of the sixth century, followed by a series of reforms under Leovigild between 572 and 586.

During the first three quarters of the sixth century, the most prominent coin type associated with the Visigothic kingdom in Spain and southern France was a gold *tremissis* featuring a profile bust on the obverse and the figure of Victory advancing across the reverse, holding a palm branch and a wreath. This series of coins includes issues from the Ostrogoths, Burgundians, and parts

*Independent researcher, Costa Rica (tecmarsa@gmail.com).

**The American Numismatic Society (dyoon@numismatics.org).

***Fellow, Paris Institute for Advanced Study. This work was carried out as a member of the research project HAR-2012-33002, financed by the Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad, Spain (ruth@pliego.eu).

of Merovingian Gaul, but it is most prominently associated with the kingdom of the Visigoths, where it seems to have been the only official type of *tremissis* issued from the time of the Byzantine emperor Anastasius I (491–518) until a major redesign of Visigothic coinage under Leovigild (568–586). Although *solidi* were also issued into the mid-sixth century,¹ the *tremissis* was the essential denomination that became the basis of Visigothic regal coinage beginning with Leovigild.

One of the essential features of the regal coinage after Leovigild's reforms was that it bore the name of the Visigothic king on the obverse and the name of the city of minting or issue on the reverse. Previously, the legends of the coins were derived, sometimes loosely, from Late Roman and Byzantine models; they indicate the name of the emperor in Constantinople rather than the Visigothic king in whose realm they were minted. These pseudo-imperial coins present significant challenges to interpretation and they have, perhaps in consequence, received less systematic attention than they deserve.

The changing weight and fineness of Visigothic regal coinage from the late sixth century to the early eighth has been extensively studied, allowing reconstruction of a sequence of debasement punctuated by occasional reforms.² Study of the weights of the pseudo-imperial coins has pointed to similarly important changes before the regal coinage;³ however, the fineness, equally important for understanding any changes in standard, has received little systematic attention.

On the basis of the weights reported for the coins compiled in his catalogue of the series of *tremisses* featuring Victory with palm and wreath, Wallace Tomasini offered the conclusion that the weight standard for Visigothic pseudo-imperial *tremisses* remained close to the theoretical Roman ideal of 1.51 grams until the time of the Byzantine emperor Justin II (565–578), when the weight standard was reduced in some but not all issues, namely JII 1, JII 2, C 3, C 4, and IR, to around 1.33 grams.⁴ Philip Grierson observed that this reduction brought

1. W. Reinhart, "Die Münzen des westgotischen Reiches von Toledo," *Deutsches Jahrbuch für Numismatik* 3–4 (1940–41): 66–101.

2. See recent summaries of the literature in R. Pliego, *La moneda visigoda* (Sevilla: Universidad de Sevilla, 2009); J. Vico et al., *Corpus nummorum visigothorum* (Madrid: J. Vico, 2006); A. Kurt, *Minting, State, and Economy in the Visigothic Kingdom* (Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, in press).

3. W. J. Tomasini, *The Barbaric Tremissis in Spain and Southern France, Anastasius to Leovigild* (New York: American Numismatic Society, 1964); D. M. Metcalf et al., "Sixth-Century Visigothic Metrology, Some Evidence from Portugal," *American Journal of Numismatics* 3–4 (1991–92): 65–90.

4. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremissis*, 152.

Visigothic *tremisses* into line with the weight standard used in the Frankish kingdom; he hypothesized that this weight around 1.3 grams represented a Germanic weight standard.⁵ Metcalf, Cabral, and Alves refined this picture, proposing a slight reduction of the weight standard to between 1.41 and 1.45 grams around 520, followed by the same larger reduction that Tomasini had noted.⁶ In addition, reporting on a small sample of coins (two *solidi* and twenty-two *tremisses*) analyzed by particle-induced X-ray emission (PIXE), they concluded that the *tremisses* were “of a very high and reliable standard of fineness, which was maintained throughout”—until a debasement at the same time as Leovigild’s introduction of the use of his own name on the obverse with the reverse legend INCLITVS REX.⁷

More recently the lead author of this article, together with Andrew Oddy and Cécile Morriçon, reviewed the metrology of Visigothic coinage from the mid-sixth century to the first quarter of the seventh, for comparison with the coins of Byzantine *Spania*, thought to have been minted in Cartagena.⁸ That study found that the Visigothic pseudo-imperial coins in the name of Justinian I had, on average, a significantly lower fineness (around 90%) than contemporary Byzantine coins from Constantinople, suggesting that some mild debasement had already occurred by the middle decades of the sixth century, which was generally mirrored by the Byzantine coins issued in Spain.⁹ A further decrease in fineness was noted for coins in the name of Justin II, along with the decrease in weight in some groups noted in previous studies.¹⁰

Thus, it appears increasingly likely that the metrological changes in Visigothic pseudo-imperial coinage are more complex than previously appreciated. In this article we present additional evidence to elucidate this problem, which we believe may give some insight into the political and economic conditions of the Visigothic kingdom in the second and third quarters of the sixth century. The principal new evidence here consists of measurements of specific gravity for the two most important hoards of pseudo-imperial *tremisses* from Spain: the Calle Cuna or Seville hoard,¹¹ buried around the end of the 540s or early 550s, and the

5. P. Grierson and M. Blackburn, *Medieval European Coinage 1: The Early Middle Ages* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1986), 30.

6. Metcalf et al., “Sixth-Century Visigothic Metrology,” 71–73.

7. Metcalf et al., “Sixth-Century Visigothic Metrology,” 83.

8. P. Bartlett et al., “The Byzantine Gold Coinage of *Spania* (Justinian I to Heraclius),” *Revue numismatique* 167 (2011): 351–401.

9. Bartlett et al., “*Spania*,” 359.

10. Bartlett et al., “*Spania*,” 360.

11. R. Pliego, “A Hoard of Late Roman and Visigothic Gold,” *Numismatic Chronicle* 176

Figure 1. Locations of findspots and mints mentioned in this article.

Zorita de los Canes or Reccopolis hoard, buried around 578 (for locations, see Figure 1).¹² These are presented here together with other available metrological data on Visigothic coinage of the second and third quarters of the sixth century.

METHODS AND METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES

The principal measure that we use to examine changes in the standards of the Visigothic pseudo-imperial *tremisses* is what we call “intrinsic value”, defined here as the mass of pure gold contained in a coin.¹³ This measure is obtained by multiplying the observed mass of the coin by a measure of the fineness of its gold alloy; thus, for example, a coin of 1.40 grams with a fineness of 86% contains 1.20 grams of gold.

Numerous methods exist for the measurement of the composition of a coin’s alloy, but they are not entirely comparable in their results.¹⁴ Each method has its drawbacks; for a variety of reasons, the new data here were produced by measurement of specific gravity. Although this method can only estimate the relative proportions of two elements, with any others assumed to be negligible or held

(2016): 377–86.

12. J. Cabré Aguiló, *El tesoro visigodo de trientes de las excavaciones del Plan Nacional de 1944–45 en Zorita de los Canes (Guadalajara)* (Madrid: Ministerio de Educación Nacional, 1946).

13. This differs from intrinsic value in a monetary sense because the principal alloying material, silver, also had “intrinsic” monetary value in the Visigothic economy, so the monetary intrinsic value of the coin will be somewhat greater than its intrinsic value in the sense used here.

14. Pliego, *Moneda visigoda*, 1.211; Bartlett et al., “Spania,” 355.

constant, it also has a number of important practical advantages.¹⁵ The method is non-destructive and requires relatively simple equipment, so that it can easily be carried out on site where the coins are located; these are important considerations when dealing with high-value gold coins. Furthermore, it is a bulk method that measures the entire coin. Other non-destructive methods such as PIXE and X-ray fluorescence (XRF) are very limited in the depth to which they can penetrate below the surface. For coins that were buried in an acidic environment or that have been cleaned using mild acids, there is typically a surface layer in which less-reactive elements (in this case gold) are enriched relative to more-reactive elements (in this case silver).¹⁶ Thus, these surface methods tend to overstate the fineness of a gold alloy.

Almost all of the new specific-gravity measurements presented in this paper were carried out by Peter Bartlett, using methods consistent with those described for his previous study of the coinage of Byzantine Spania.¹⁷ The few exceptions were done by others (see Appendix 3), in consultation with Bartlett regarding procedures. The immersion liquid used was perfluoro-1-methyldecalin, and the density of the liquid was calibrated by use of a .9999 fine Canadian Maple Leaf gold bullion coin as a reference standard. However, the coins were not rigorously cleaned, and traces of dirt or other surface contaminants may cause some specific gravity readings to understate the fineness of the alloy by up to 3%.¹⁸

Additional measurements of fineness published by previous researchers have been included in this article where relevant. Specific gravity measurements for Visigothic coins in the Fitzwilliam Museum, Cambridge, were carried out by W. A. Oddy using comparable methods.¹⁹ Many of the specific gravity measurements of Visigothic coins reported in the previous article on Byzantine Spania were carried out by Lauris Olson, using trifluorotrchloroethane (Freon 113) as the immersion liquid, which is denser than distilled water but less dense than perfluoro-1-methyldecalin.²⁰ However, some PIXE and XRF milliprobe analyses represent surface measurements that are less directly comparable with specific gravity; we have included them for the sake of completeness, but they are likely

15. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 352–56; T. Jonson et al., "The Byzantine Mint in Carthage and the Islamic Mint in North Africa," *Revue numismatique* 171 (2014): 655–99.

16. Jonson et al., "Byzantine Mint," 661–62.

17. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 352–56.

18. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 356–57.

19. Grierson and Blackburn, *MEC* 1, 415.

20. Olson previously made these measurements available on his website; they can be seen at <http://web.archive.org/web/20020704103330/http://pobox.upenn.edu/~olson/visicoins/ansvpw.prn>

to be systematically somewhat higher than the other measurements.²¹ This matters most for the coins of lower fineness; in practice, coins whose composition is more than 90% gold do not differ greatly when surface methods are compared with specific gravity because there is very little room for surface enrichment, and so we consider the results for such coins to be comparable.

Along with intrinsic value, the other crucial variable for this article is time, and this presents greater difficulties. The closing dates of the two hoards nicely bracket the third quarter of the sixth century. However, hoards may contain coins of various ages, there may have been significant changes at dates between 550 and 578, and one would like to compare the hoard coins to other coins of similar date. The imitative nature of the pseudo-imperial coinage creates significant uncertainties for dating. Two kinds of information are available, both of which must be used with caution: the imperial name on the obverse and the style.

For the past several decades, this series has been understood in large part through reference to Wallace J. Tomasini's 1964 monograph on the topic.²² His work was a major advance in the classification of these coins, although it has not escaped criticism. An art historian originally specializing in Renaissance Italy, Tomasini brought an acute eye for stylistic relationships to the problem of organizing this difficult series.

Tomasini's system begins with the Byzantine emperor named in the obverse legend. This provides a rough chronological framework (Anastasius I–Justin I–Justinian I–Justin II), but it cannot be assumed that a coin with Anastasius I's name was struck during Anastasius I's reign. The imperial accessions at least provide *termini post quem* for the use of each emperor's name, but it is unlikely that all the moneymen in the Visigothic kingdom were punctilious about keeping their dies up to date with changes of ruler in Constantinople. Although the relative sequence seems to have been followed, it is possible that some moneymen were still producing coins with a garbled version of Justinian's name several years into the reign of Justin II, for example, at the same time that others were using some approximation of Justin's name. Moreover, as spelling departed increasingly from the official norms, it can sometimes be difficult to decide which emperor's name, if any, was intended.

Toward the end of the sequence there are many coins whose legends either are not interpretable as names or refer to a Visigothic king, Leovigild or Her-

21. D. M. Metcalf and F. Schweizer, "Milliprobe Analyses of Some Visigothic, Suevic, and Other Gold Coins of the Early Middle Ages," *Archaeometry* 12 (1970): 173–87; Metcalf et al., "Sixth-Century Visigothic Metrology."

22. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremissis*.

menegild, instead of an emperor. Some of these are separated out by Tomasini into special categories, whereas others are grouped with stylistically similar coins that bear an imperial name. Thus, Tomasini's categories partly change with the introduction of the king's name and partly overlap that process.

Within the major periods defined by imperial reigns, Tomasini identified a number of stylistic clusters, which form the basis of his classification system. These clusters have a core group of coins that stylistically share clear resemblances to each other and clear differences from other clusters, but they often have fuzzy edges, where coins share some traits with the core of the cluster but also have significant differences. Sometimes Tomasini included such coins in the main type, other times he separated them into subtypes. There is little debate about the core coins of the major types; Tomasini's classification usefully brings together many coins of clear stylistic affinities. The number of coins that do not fit the types well is substantial, though, and the sometimes vague boundaries and definitions of the types often make it difficult to apply Tomasini's classification in practice.

Tomasini also suggested possible mint attributions for his major types. These mint attributions are not based on his stylistic interpretations—in fact, if one follows the relationships between styles that he proposed, the stylistic traditions do not show much tendency to be associated with regions. Instead, these mint attributions are based largely on prior work by Wilhelm Reinhart, Pierre Le Gentilhomme and, for the coins with the name of Leovigild, George Miles.²³ Thus, the minting locations proposed by Tomasini can be followed or revised independently of the validity of the types.

In many cases Tomasini followed a model proposed by Reinhart, according to which the principal mint of each king's reign is expected to be the city where that king is believed to have had his principal residence. This model has a number of drawbacks, as Tomasini recognized. As soon as mint names were placed on coins by Leovigild, it can be seen that numerous mints were active, and the royal residence of Toledo was only one of several major mints.²⁴ The stylistic diversity documented by Tomasini, with what appear to be several distinct workshop traditions, suggests that multiple mints co-existed before Leovigild as well.

Therefore we have treated Tomasini's categories as stylistic traditions of learning that existed over an extended, though uncertain, length of time. These stylis-

23. Reinhart, "Münzen"; P. Le Gentilhomme, "Le monnayage et la circulation monétaire dans les royaumes barbares en Occident (V^e-VIII^e siècle)," *Revue numismatique* 7 (1943): 46-112, 8 (1944-45): 13-59; G. Miles, *The Coinage of the Visigoths of Spain, Leovigild to Achila II* (New York: American Numismatic Society, 1952).

24. Pliego, *Moneda visigoda*, 2.27.

tic traditions probably correspond in part to practices of training within specific workshops, perhaps ramifying on occasion when a new mint was established by sending a few mint personnel from an existing location. There remains considerable room for discussion about the definition of and relationships between these categories, and the hypotheses about the relationships between groups that Tomasini proposed in his monograph. For Tomasini's major categories of the period under discussion in this article, one can see several separate traditions, including JAN 4 leading to JII 4, a JAN 1/JAN 2/JAN 7/JAN 8 cluster leading to C 1/C 2, JAN 5 leading to JII 2 and probably also JII 3, and others whose connections are less clear, such as JAN 3 (probably a predecessor of some of the other JAN types), JII 5 of uncertain origin, and C 3/C 4—derived from the earliest JAN 2/JAN 8 styles—leading to IR and H 2/H 3.²⁵

This leaves many coins of uncertain affinities, often of relatively crude workmanship. This would seem to suggest that goldsmiths or other metal workers unconnected with the major mints were capable of producing small issues of coins, loosely copied from examples in circulation, either on an official basis or unofficially.

Although Tomasini's classification and his inferences about stylistic relationships might benefit from a thorough review, given the substantial increase in evidence since 1964, that is beyond the scope of this article. Here we follow his major types as the basic framework for our discussion of the metrological changes during the third quarter of the sixth century, simply because they are currently the most detailed system that attempts to group coins according to the workshops, mints, or regions that produced them, even if we generally do not have a clear idea of where these were.

THE CALLE CUNA HOARD

This hoard was found during construction work in 1972 at Calle Cuna 46 in Seville.²⁶ A total of seventy-seven gold coins were recovered by the authorities, out of seventy-eight coins originally present in the hoard. The largest component was forty-one Roman Imperial *solidi*, two in the name of Arcadius (383–408) and thirty-nine in the name of Honorius (393–423), all from the mint of Milan.²⁷ Analysis of the Roman *solidi* indicates a high fineness (99% average) but

25. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremissis*, 288; D. Yoon, "Evolution of Stylistic Patterns in Pre-Visigothic Tremisses," Paper presented at the XV International Numismatic Congress, Taormina, Italy, 2015.

26. Pliego, "Hoard," 377.

27. Pliego, "Hoard," 378–80.

a weight (average 4.34 g²⁸) somewhat less than the original theoretical weight of 4.50 grams,²⁹ undoubtedly due to wear from circulation during the approximately 150 years between minting and deposition.

The rest of the coins—thirteen *solidi* and twenty-three *tremisses*—are pseudo-imperial issues attributable to the Visigoths. These are presented in Appendix 1.

The Visigothic *solidi*—one each in the name of Anastasius I (491–518) and Justin I (518–527) and eleven in the name of Justinian I (527–565)—are mostly of a type identified by Reinhart as Visigothic, with a reverse showing Victory standing left, holding a staff surmounted by a staurogram and normally forked at the base after 520.³⁰ Based on reported find locations including the Calle Cuna hoard, Metcalf thought the center of distribution of this type was lower Baetica.³¹ The *solidus* in the name of Anastasius (Pliego no. 42) and two in the name of Justinian (nos. 54 and 62) differ in having Victory holding a voided jeweled cross. These may be from another mint, but the number of finds with reported locations is too small to identify a specific region such as Tarraconensis, Narbonensis, or central Spain.

The Visigoths appear not to have coined *solidi* after the time of Justinian I, and even for the period from Anastasius to Justinian the *solidi* are generally much rarer than the *tremisses*.³² In the case of Calle Cuna, the thirteen Visigothic *solidi*, being equivalent to thirty-nine *tremisses*, were of greater total value than the twenty-three *tremisses*. However, the fineness of the individual *solidi* was also greater than that of the *tremisses* (mean 98% for the *solidi* versus 95% for the *tremisses*).³³ That there were two different standards of fineness at this period was noted by Metcalf, who suggested that the *solidi* may have been kept closer to the Byzantine standard for use in Mediterranean trade,³⁴ although to our knowledge this type has not been found outside the Iberian Peninsula.

28. The weights recorded by Bartlett while carrying out the specific gravity measurements show occasional minor differences from the weights reported previously in Pliego, “Hoard.” Since Bartlett’s weights are the ones used in the calculation of specific gravity, we follow those in this article.

29. J. P. C. Kent, *Roman Imperial Coinage X* (London: Spink and Son, 1994), 12.

30. Reinhart, “Münzen,” 76–80.

31. Metcalf et al., “Sixth-Century Visigothic Metrology,” 82.

32. Grierson and Blackburn, *MEC 1*, 48.

33. The coins from this hoard have been analyzed by XRF at the Centro Nacional de Aceleradores (Seville). We await their publication to see whether this method also found the difference in fineness between the *solidi* and *tremisses*. The same researchers may also have analyzed some coins from the Zorita hoard, which could indicate whether there is enough copper in the alloy to require adjustment of the specific gravity calculations (above 2%).

34. Metcalf et al., “Sixth-Century Visigothic Metrology,” 82.

Of the twenty-three *tremisses* in the Calle Cuna hoard, eight can be classified with Tomasini's Justin I categories.³⁵ The remaining fifteen coins can be classified with Tomasini's Justinian I categories.³⁶ The average intrinsic values for the coins in the names of Justin I (1.37 g Au) and Justinian I (1.38 g Au) are essentially equal, giving no indication of any change during the second quarter of the sixth century. As a whole, the twenty-three *tremisses* had a mean fineness of 95.3% (range 94 to 98%, with standard deviation of 1.2) and a mean weight of 1.446 g (range 1.424 to 1.464 g, standard deviation 0.013), resulting in a mean intrinsic value of 1.38 g Au (range 1.34 to 1.42 g, standard deviation 0.025).

Bartlett et al.³⁷ summarized previously published alloy measurements of sixteen Visigothic *tremisses* in the name of Justinian I from the Ashmolean and Fitzwilliam Museums. These had an average weight of 1.376 g and fineness 93.4%, for an average intrinsic value of 1.29 g Au, which is 6% lower than the intrinsic value of 1.38 g Au for the Calle Cuna *tremisses*. The difference in fineness is only 2% (95.3% for Calle Cuna, 93.4% for the other Justinian-type coins). The major proportion of the difference in intrinsic value comes from the weights, with a 5% difference (1.446 g for Calle Cuna coins and 1.376 g for the other sixteen coins). The burial date for the Calle Cuna hoard was most likely in the turmoil between the murder of Theudis in 548 and that of Agila in 554, so if the Ashmolean and Fitzwilliam coins are largely later than that, it would suggest that the last ten or fifteen years of Justinian's reign saw a reduction in the standard of Visigothic *tremisses*.³⁸

In summary, the Calle Cuna hoard, with a wide range of types present, makes it clear that both weight and fineness, and thus the intrinsic value, of the Vi-

35. One of these coins, Pliego no. 43, could be grouped either with Anastasius (type A 3), where it probably shares an obverse die with Tomasini no. 82, or with Justin I (type JI 1c), where it is a die duplicate of Tomasini nos. 171 and 172. Some of these JI coins, such as Pliego no. 50 (Pl. 27, 1), could date to the early years of Justinian's reign: Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremisses*, 98.

36. Most of these fifteen coins belong either to Tomasini's JAN 3 group (Pl. 27, 2) or to the cluster of closely related groups called JAN 1, JAN 2 (Pl. 27, 3-4), and JAN 8 (Pl. 27, 5). Most likely either JAN 3 or the JAN 1/2/8 cluster was local to Seville or its region, but until more evidence of find locations is available, it is not clear which one.

37. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 387.

38. This is also suggested by the Byzantine coins of Spania in the name of Justinian, which must have been produced after the Byzantine intervention, recently redated to 554: J. Fossella, "'Waiting Only for a Pretext': A New Chronology for the Sixth-Century Byzantine Invasion of Spain," *Estudios Bizantinos* 1 (2013): 30-38. The Byzantine coins of Spania appear to follow approximately the standard of the Visigothic coins circulating at the same time: Bartlett et al., "Spania." In this case, the mean weight of the Byzantine coins was 2% higher than those of Calle Cuna, but the fineness was 5% lower, resulting in a slightly lower intrinsic value.

sigothic *tremisses* were high throughout the second quarter of the sixth century, well into the reign of Justinian I. This partially supports Metcalf's conclusion that the fineness remained high,³⁹ though only up to the middle of the sixth century. The results would point to stability in the weight and fineness of the coinage during the "Ostrogothic interval" under the rule of Theudis (531–548). The low standard deviations in weight and fineness further indicate effective control over the minting process. To determine what happened during the third quarter of the century we must look to other sources, and in particular to the hoard of Zorita de los Canes.

THE ZORITA HOARD

This hoard of ninety *tremisses* was found in 1944 during an archaeological excavation by Juan Cabré at the site of Cerro de la Oliva near Zorita de los Canes, which is believed to have been the Visigothic city of Reccopolis, founded by Leovigild in 578.⁴⁰ Cabré associated the hoard with a destruction that he dated around 580–83, but a subsequent re-analysis of the evidence during more recent excavations by Lauro Olmo Enciso has made it clear that this date is untenable. Instead, the hoard must have been deposited during construction associated with the founding of the city, thus in 578–79.⁴¹ It therefore could be expected to contain coins primarily minted in the third quarter of the sixth century; most importantly, it closes in the middle of the reign of Leovigild, after his changes to the coinage had begun but before they were completed.

Cabré catalogued the coins from 1 to 90; the numbering of his catalogue is also the basis for the coins' inventory numbers in the Museo Arqueológico Nacional (1968/30/1 to 1968/30/90). We will refer to them by these numbers, as Zorita 1 through 90, in our discussion below.

Several scholars have tackled the classification of the coins of this hoard (see Appendix 2). Cabré divided them in two general categories; his Group 1 consists of coins that he considered to be non-Visigothic (Zorita 1–7) and some coins he considered Visigothic but alien in character, possibly from Narbonensis (Zorita 8–12). The remainder of the coins he placed in Group 2 in a chronologically ordered set of categories based on his interpretation of the legends: Group 2a

39. Metcalf et al., "Sixth-Century Visigothic Metrology," 83: "Until we reach the transitional types, the indications are of a uniform alloy."

40. Cabré, *Tesorillo*; Ioh. Biclár., *Chron.* 50.

41. L. Olmo Enciso, "Fuentes escritas y primeras investigaciones sobre Recópolis," in *Recópolis y la ciudad en la época visigoda*, edited by L. Olmo (Alcalá de Henares: Museo Arqueológico Regional, 2008), 23–39; M. Castro Priego, "Reccopolis y los contextos numismáticos de época visigoda en el Centro de la Península Ibérica," *Revue numismatique* 171 (2014): 463–95.

in the name of Justinian (Zorita 13–26), Groups 2b and 2c in the name of Justin II (Zorita 27–67), and Group 2d, his “serie Primitiva Leovigildiana” (Zorita 68–90), which he believed to have been minted between 568 and 580 with either indecipherable legends or the name of Liuva I (568–572) or Leovigild.⁴² Tomasini included the Zorita hoard in his study, with some of his stylistic groups and subgroups from the period of Justin II being defined largely on the basis of the Zorita evidence.⁴³ Barral included the hoard in his study of monetary circulation, proposing his own interpretations of the legends in some cases.⁴⁴ It is clear from the three classifications presented in Appendix 2 that there is not complete agreement about how to interpret some of the legends; this is not surprising due to the often erratic spellings used.

In order to examine the process of change in Visigothic coinage during the third quarter of the sixth century, we present the evidence from the Zorita hoard not as a single group but in relation to the stylistic groups of Tomasini’s classification. We also present measurements of non-hoard coins at the same time, for comparison to the Zorita evidence. Where possible, we attempt to relate differences in gold content to other variables, such as stylistic differences.

Coins in the Name of Justinian

No coins in the name of Anastasius were present and those that appear to bear the name of Justin are attributed to Justin II (565–578); thus, the earliest coins in the Zorita hoard should be those in the name of Justinian I (527–565). Tomasini placed six of the Zorita coins (Zorita 20 to 25) in his JAN 2 group and one (Z 26) in subgroup JAN 2b, as well as four coins (Zorita 15, 17, 18, and 29) in JAN 5.

JAN 2

Tomasini’s JAN 2 category is a major group, with thirty examples in Tomasini’s catalogue, plus nine others in imitative or vaguely related JAN 2 subgroups. Since 1964, numerous other JAN 2 coins have been published; of particular interest are several from the Calle Cuna hoard.⁴⁵ Based on its abundance, JAN 2 is likely to represent one of the major mints of the Visigothic kingdom during the time of Justinian.

Tomasini dated his JAN 2 category to the 530s, believing that it formed part of a sequence preceded by JAN 1 and followed by JAN 8 and then the Curru coins.

42. Cabré, *Tesorillo*.

43. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremissis*.

44. X. Barral i Altet, *La circulation des monnaies suèves et visigothiques* (München: Artemis, 1976), 86–92.

45. Pliego, “Hoard.”

The presence of this type in the Zorita hoard does not fit this dating, as Tomasini was aware, and he suggested that the Zorita examples were very late examples of the JAN 2 type that might date to around 550.⁴⁶ Based on his dating, Tomasini proposed that the JAN 2 group was minted in Barcelona, and the closely related JAN 8 group, which he dated to the reign of Athanagild, in Toledo.⁴⁷

However, the evidence of the Calle Cuna hoard provides a clear picture of the JAN 2 group around 550, and this requires a revision of Tomasini's proposed dates. The JAN 2 coins in the Calle Cuna hoard belong stylistically at the early end of the type. The JAN 2 coins from Zorita appear, as Tomasini noted, to be late in the sequence stylistically. Thus, it would seem that the JAN 2 type should be dated later than Tomasini proposed, from the 540s to the 560s. This has two further consequences. First, it breaks the connection with the reign of Theudis, whom Tomasini supposed to have resided in Barcelona. This was Tomasini's basis for attributing the type to Barcelona, so the question of where it was minted remains open. Given the presence of several examples in the Calle Cuna hoard, a southern origin must be considered a possibility, although there are also some known finds in northern Spain and southern France.⁴⁸ And second, the proposed sequence from JAN 2 to JAN 8 no longer fits the available time frame, and these two groups should instead be seen as roughly coeval.

The six Zorita coins attributed by Tomasini to JAN 2 are compared in Appendix 3.1 with eleven others for which the intrinsic value is known. Substantial changes in composition can be seen within the JAN 2 category, as would be expected for a type that spanned the reigns from Theudis to Athanagild, rather than just from the time of Theudis. The five JAN 2 coins from Calle Cuna have an intrinsic value of 1.38 g Au (range 1.37 to 1.39, SD 0.023). Eleven JAN 2 coins that are from neither hoard have an average intrinsic value of 1.28 g (range 1.13 to 1.36, SD 0.071). However, the six JAN 2 coins from Zorita have a mean fineness of 76% (range 63 to 82%, SD 8.1) and a mean weight of 1.19 g (range 1.04 to 1.35 g, SD of 0.13 g), resulting in a mean intrinsic value of only 0.90 g (range 0.81 to 1.00, SD 0.079).

Within the Zorita hoard there is a further distinction to be made. The four JAN 2 coins from Zorita 22 to 25 are generally well made using similar techniques to other JAN 2 coins, in a style that is more abstract and linear than most but otherwise comparable. On the other hand, Zorita 20 and 21, while similar

46. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremisses*, 162.

47. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremisses*, 164.

48. E.g., V. Geneviève, "Découverte de deux *tremisses* visigothiques," in *D'Iluo à Oloron-Sainte-Marie*, eds. D. Barraud and F. Réchin (Pessac: Fédération Aquitania, 2013), 383–96; M. Crusafont et al., "Silver Visigothic Coinage," *Numismatic Chronicle* 176 (2016): 241–60.

to each other, are distinct from the others with a relatively simplified style and crude technique, most noticeably not using triangular, circular, and arc-shaped punches in the manner normal for JAN 2. The fineness parallels this stylistic difference; Zorita 20 and 21 have finenesses of 63% and 68% for an average of 65.5% Au, while the other four average 81% Au (range 79 to 82%).

A possible interpretation for the JAN 2 coins from Zorita is that the four from Zorita 22 to 25 (see Pl. 27, 6, Zorita 23) are late products of the same school of engravers that produced the Calle Cuna and other JAN 2 coins, and that up until ca. 550 the fineness was high (94 to 96%), but that sometime between then and ca. 565 it was lowered to around 80% (with some ANS and Fitzwilliam coins showing an intermediate fineness around 90%). The other two coins, Zorita 20 and 21 (see Pl. 27, 7, Zorita 21), may have been the product of another engraver, possibly unofficial or working at a different mint, copying the JAN 2 style but at a significantly reduced fineness.

Zorita 26 (Pl. 27, 8) is another relatively crude coin in a style reminiscent of JAN 2 but technically divergent. Tomasini assigned it to his rather disparate JAN 2b subgroup, which he suggested to be unofficial products. This coin has a fineness of 64%, a weight of 1.275 g, and thus an intrinsic value of 0.82 g, making it similar to Zorita 20 and 21.

JAN 5

Tomasini's JAN 5 category is another major group from the time of Justinian's reign, with twenty-eight examples in Tomasini's catalogue. As with JAN 2, numerous examples have appeared since 1964, some with known findspots; however, it is worth noting that no examples were found in the Calle Cuna hoard. Tomasini proposed that JAN 5 should be dated to the late 540s and 550s and was minted at Seville, but its absence from the Calle Cuna hoard suggests some modification at least.

There is clear continuity between JAN 5 and JII 2, which is stylistically similar but has a name on the obverse most easily read as that of Justin, presumably Justin II. This makes it likely that JAN 5 should date to the latter part of Justinian's reign, after 550 and perhaps closer to 560, and without the proposed connection to Theudis and Theudigisel, the basis for attributing this type to Seville is lacking. Based on a recent find of multiple examples in northeastern Spain, an origin in Tarraconensis may be considered a possibility.⁴⁹

The four coins from Zorita (Zorita 15, 17, 18, and 29) that Tomasini placed in his group JAN 5 are compared in values in Appendix 3.2 with nine other JAN 5

49. Crusafont et al., "Silver Visigothic Coinage."

coins for which the specific gravity has been measured. The mean fineness of the four Zorita coins is 76% Au (range 60 to 87%, SD 11.5) and the mean weight is 1.11 g (range 0.99 to 1.38 g, SD 0.18), giving a mean intrinsic value of 0.83 g (range 0.81 to 0.86 g, SD 0.022). The nine JAN 5 coins not from Zorita had a mean fineness of 88% Au (range 75 to 93%, SD 6.0) and a mean weight of 1.28 g (range 0.91 to 1.43 g, SD 0.22), giving a mean intrinsic value of 1.14 g (range of 0.79 to 1.31 g, SD 0.021). The nine JAN 5 coins not from Zorita are lower than the eleven JAN 2 coins not from Zorita in both fineness and weight and thus in intrinsic value: 1.14 g for JAN 5 versus 1.28 g for JAN 2. If JAN 5 coins are later than JAN 2 on average, as would be suggested by the absence of JAN 5 from the Calle Cuna hoard, this would support the hypothesis of a slight reduction toward the end of the Justinian series.

As with JAN 2, the four Zorita JAN 5 coins are lower in gold than the other nine examples, averaging only 0.83 g of Au versus 1.14 g Au. Of the four, three (see Pl. 28, 9, Zorita 18) seem to parallel the other JAN 5 coins in style while Zorita 15 (Pl. 28, 10) has some features that point in the direction of JII 3. Zorita 15 is also notably different from the other three in having a heavier weight of 1.38 g but a much lower fineness of only 60%; however, this gives an intrinsic value close to the average of the other three. Given the difference in style, weight, and fineness it would seem likely that Zorita 15 might be the work of a different engraver or workshop, possibly related to the origin of the JII 3 style. The other three JAN 5 coins from Zorita, probably minted close to the end of reign of Justinian (November 565), again suggest a significant devaluation close to the end of the important JAN 5 series.

Coins from the Time of Justin II

By the time of Justin II's reign (565–578), many die-sinkers in the Visigothic kingdom no longer attempted to replicate the Byzantine emperor's name with any clarity; the legends are often difficult to interpret and sometimes have no apparent linguistic interpretation but should be seen as abstract patterns of forms, such as IVIVIVIVIVI or VRRVONTIOVRYV. Nevertheless, for legends that are not fully abstract, the sequence of letters and position of the usual break over the head of the imperial bust usually make it possible to distinguish legends derived from types of Justinian versus legends derived from types of Justin II.

No coins of Tomasini's JII 1 category were found in the Zorita hoard. It is a small group, with only three examples in Tomasini's catalogue. It is stylistically conservative and probably should be considered early within Justin II's reign.

JII 2

Tomasini's JII 2 category is a relatively large group of twenty-four coins, of which eighteen (75%) are from Zorita. This group is very closely related to the JAN 5 category, which differs mainly in having a legend recognizable as the name of Justinian I on the obverse. However, this is a stylistically diverse group, with some examples very similar to JAN 5 and others merging at the edges with other crudely engraved categories from the time of Justin II, such as JII 7 and JII 3.

The eighteen JII 2 coins from the Zorita hoard presented in Appendix 3.3 have a mean fineness of 77% Au (range 53% to 92%, SD 12.2) and a mean weight of 1.15 g (range 0.77 to 1.43 g, SD 0.18), resulting in a mean intrinsic value of 0.87 grams (range 0.60 to 1.14 g, SD 0.14). The low intrinsic value represents a considerable reduction (37%) from the time of the Calle Cuna hoard. The large variation measured by the standard deviation indicates poor control over the minting process. The difference in fineness (77% versus 87%) between Zorita 40 and 41, struck from the same obverse die, further emphasizes the poor control over the composition of the alloy. Zorita 27, 28, 30, 31, 37, 38, 40, 41, 42, 44, and 48 (and possibly also Zorita 32) are stylistically similar (see Pl. 28, 11–12, Zorita 40 and 41), but Zorita 49 is very crude, and Zorita 43, 46, 50, and 51 (see Pl. 28, 13–15, Zorita 43, 50, and 51) seem stylistically different. Some of the coins may chronologically belong with the Justinian groups, in particular the high-value ones.

Two coins included by Tomasini in his JII 2 category that are not from the Zorita hoard, both in the Gabinet Numismàtic de Catalunya,⁵⁰ have been measured for specific gravity: Amorós 9 with a fineness of 78% and Amorós 18 with 94% Au.⁵¹ However, there is some reason to question whether either of them should be grouped with the Zorita JII 2 coins. Amorós 9 is a coin whose obverse legend reads Δ NIIVSTN Λ VSP Λ . Both the break and the Λ would suggest that the legend refers to Justinian, making this coin a JAN 5. Its metrology would fit in with the fineness, weight, and intrinsic value of the four Zorita JAN 5 coins, although not with the non-Zorita JAN 5 coins. Amorós 18 is quite different in style from the typical JII 2 coins, and with a high fineness and weight, its intrinsic value of 1.29 g Au does not fit in well with the JII 2 coins from the Zorita hoard.

Tomasini also defined two subgroups related to the JII 2 group, JII 2a (see Pl. 28, 16, Zorita 45) and JII 2b; each is composed of three coins, all from Zorita. Both of these groups are crudely engraved imitations of the JII 2 style, and

50. J. Amorós and A. Mata Berruezo, *Catálogo de las monedas visigodas del Gabinete Numismático de Cataluña* (Barcelona: Ayuntamiento de Barcelona, 1952), nos. 9 and 18.

51. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 388–89.

Tomasini suggested that the JII 2b group in particular may be unofficial imitative coins.⁵² The JII 2a coins have a mean fineness of 72% Au and mean weight of 1.21 g, for a mean intrinsic value of 0.86 g. The JII 2b coins with a mean fineness of 55% Au and mean weight of 1.40 g, for a mean intrinsic value of 0.77 g. They may represent different issues and both follow the trend of a lowering of the intrinsic value found in the Zorita JII coins.

JII 3

This is another sizable category in Tomasini's classification, with twenty-five coins in his catalogue, of which sixteen (64%) are from the Zorita hoard. Stylistically it is more coherent than JII 2, but the obverse heads range from examples that are naturalistic in style (Pl. 29, 17, Zorita 53) to examples that are almost cubist in abstraction (Pl. 29, 18, Zorita 33). Some of this stylistic diversity may, as Tomasini suggested, represent a sequence of change over time.⁵³ There are a surprising number of die links in this group in the Zorita hoard, unlike any other of the large groups. This could indicate that it was a relatively small issue or that the JII 3 coins came from a mint close to Zorita and did not circulate for long before they were incorporated into the hoard.

The sixteen Zorita JII 3 coins presented in Appendix 3.4 have a mean fineness of 51% Au (range 42% to 74%, SD 8.6), and a mean weight of 1.35 g (range 0.97 to 1.49 g, SD 0.13), resulting in a mean intrinsic value of 0.68 g (range 0.52 to 0.93 g, SD 0.10). The intrinsic value for the JII 3 coins is lower than that of the JII 2 (mean 0.87 g) by a third (33%) and is only 50% of the intrinsic value of the Calle Cuna coins (1.38 g Au). Of the sixteen coins, two are considerably higher in Au than the rest, Zorita 13 (74%) and 14 (65%), both of which Cabré had classified under Justinian along with Zorita 16. The latter (Zorita 16) is from the same dies as Zorita 53, 54, and 55 and clearly belongs with them. The obverse legend for Zorita 13 reads DNIVSTNI NVSPASVC , only lacking an Λ at 12 o'clock for Justinian. Zorita 14 does not offer a clear IVSTINVS either, so there could be some doubt to the exact placement of these two coins with the others. If these two coins are removed, the standard deviation of the remaining fourteen coins is reduced from 0.100 to 0.078.

With numerous die links and die duplications among the JII 3 coins of the Zorita hoard, we have a good opportunity to look at the degree of control exercised over the Au content in minting process for this group. There is a group of

52. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremisses*, 119.

53. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremisses*, 119–21.

four coins from the same pair of dies (Zorita 16, 53, 54, and 55) and two coins from another pair of dies (Zorita 62 and 63). Zorita 35 and 36 share the same obverse die, and Zorita 59 and 60 share another obverse die. The finenesses of Zorita 16, 53, 54, and 55 are in a fairly narrow range from 45% to 49% Au. However, the finenesses for Zorita 62 (Pl. 29, 19) and 63 are 49% and 42% Au, while those for Zorita 59 (Pl. 29, 20) and 60 are 44% and 55%. The wide range in fineness for these pairs of die-linked coins indicates that, in addition to being very low, the fineness is also quite variable and not well controlled. The standard deviation of the fineness of JII 3 is 8.6 compared to that for Calle Cuna of 1.234, again emphasizing the greater variability of the JII 3 coins. The standard deviation of the weights, 0.134, is also considerably greater than that of the Calle Cuna coins (0.0245), indicating that control over the minting process had deteriorated. We point this out here because this group is more homogenous in style and has numerous die links, but this variability is a common characteristic of the Zorita coins.

Of the nine coins not from Zorita that Tomasini included in JII 3, the specific gravity of three has been measured (Tomasini nos. 450, 452, and 453, see Appendix 3.4b). The coins are all in different collections now, but at least two of them can be traced back to Wilhelm Reinhart's collection. All three show nearly identical finenesses (93 to 94%), which is much higher than that of the Zorita coins. This is striking and very difficult to understand if they came from the same mint, unless there was a change of standard toward the end of the period when this series was produced, as will be shown below for some of the other groups associated with the early reforms of Leovigild.

JII 4

Tomasini's JII 4 category is a substantial group with seventeen examples in his catalogue. It is stylistically distinctive and spans the introduction of Leovigild's name. Of the seventeen examples listed by Tomasini, only one has a legend referring to Justin II; seven have legends consisting of repetitive strings of the letters I, V, and N, whereas nine have legends referring to Leovigild, usually on both obverse and reverse. Only one coin from the Zorita hoard (Zorita 87) belongs to the main JII 4 group, which is likely to have been the product of a major mint operating during the early part of Leovigild's reign. Grierson⁵⁴ suggested there may be some similarities in the style with that of the Cross on Steps coins produced at Emerita. The stylistic similarities are difficult to specify precisely, but several JII 4 coins are known from Portuguese collections, which would fit with a

54. Grierson and Blackburn, *MEC* 1, 441, no. 203.

western location for the mint. Tomasini also identified two subgroups, JII 4a and JII 4b, whose relationship to the main JII 4 group is uncertain, but JII 4a includes two more coins from the Zorita hoard (Zorita 74 and 86).

For the main JII 4 group, the measurements for nine coins are presented in Appendix 3.5. There appears to have been a distinct change in both the weight and fineness, resulting in different intrinsic values for the meaningless-legend type (Pl. 29, 21) and the type with the name of Leovigild (Pl. 29, 22). For the six coins of the meaningless-legend type, the mean fineness is 92% Au and the mean weight 1.36 g, for a mean intrinsic value of 1.25 g. The standard deviation is relatively low (0.056), indicating a mint with good control over weight and alloy. For the three coins with the name of Leovigild, the fineness is 72% and 79% for the two coins measured by specific gravity, while for the third the PIXE surface method gave a value of 87%, which could be on the order of 10% higher due to surface enhancement.⁵⁵ The mean weight is 1.27 g for the three coins, with a mean intrinsic value of 0.97 g for the two coins measured by specific gravity. Thus, a clear change in standard occurred around the time the legends were changed to include the name of Leovigild, with a reduction of more than 20% in the gold content of the *tremissis*.

Two coins of JII 4a are from Zorita—Zorita 74 and 86—with finenesses of 60% and 76% and weights of 1.007 and 1.177 g, resulting in intrinsic values of 0.60 g and 0.89 g, respectively. Cabré and Barral thought these two coins might be of Leovigild, but the values do not correspond well with any of the early coins of Leovigild and the style for this group is difficult to relate to other coins.

JII 5

Tomasini's JII 5 category is an important group, not only because it is a substantial issue (twenty-three examples in Tomasini's catalogue, with more than twice that number known today) but also because it has a die link across the transition from coins without and with the name of Leovigild. No coins from the JII 5 group were found in the Zorita hoard, although there were two coins of a vaguely related style that Tomasini called JII 5b; these are unlikely to belong to the same issue.

The authors have been working on a die study of JII 5 coins and currently have data on more than 50 coins. The category can be divided on the basis of the obverse bust and reverse legend into three types, which we call types I, II, and III. In type I the obverse bust is drawn with ornamentation inside the rectangular body as a triangle with the apex pointing down to the top of the pectoral cross

55. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 355.

(Pl. 29, 23). In types II and III the obverse bust is ornamented with curved lines that form a roughly triangular frame above the pectoral cross, but with the apex at the top (Pl. 29, 24). Type III is differentiated from type II by the legend on the reverse. The reverse of types I and II is recognizably derived from the original VICTORIA AVGVSTORVM, generally approximating VICTVA TORVA followed by a Θ-like mark which was originally the B from the exergual CONOB but has migrated up to join the end of the reverse legend. The R is formed with a small circular punch and two symmetrically placed triangles below; it is a distinctive and idiosyncratic letterform that suggests a single die-sinker or workshop. In type III that reverse legend is replaced by a new one approximating VCLIVVIGILDIREGIS (Pl. 29, 25). The obverse legends all read IIIVSTI IIIAVA, as in types I and II, which is interpreted to refer to Justin II.

There is a die link between types II and III (see Pl. 29, 24 and 25). An example of type II in the Ashmolean Museum (Tomasini no. 515, Metcalf and Schweizer no. O.170) shares the same obverse die as an example of type III in the Museo Arqueológico Nacional, Madrid (MAN 105318). In the type III piece the obverse die shows considerable die rust and wear; this later die state indicates that type III follows type II. A link between types I and II has not been found yet, but we would suggest that type I was first.

There is a clear change in both weight and fineness from types I and II to type III, as can be seen in Appendix 3.6. The mean weights of types I and II are 1.46 g and 1.47 g, respectively, while that of type III is near 1.30 g—the mean is 1.33 g, but this is influenced by one outlier of 1.47 g, perhaps caught in transition, without which the mean is 1.299 g. The fineness of types I and II is 96% and 93%, respectively, whereas that of type III is 87%. Thus, the mean intrinsic value decreased from 1.40 g and 1.37 g in types I and II, respectively, to 1.16 g in type III, a reduction of more than 15%. The standard deviations of the intrinsic value for the three types—0.05, 0.013, and 0.058—indicate the consistent control over the minting process that one would expect in a major mint.

JII 5b

Tomasini placed two Zorita coins, Zorita 75 and 80, in his JII 5b subcategory. One of the two, Zorita 80, appears to be an imitation of the JII 5 type from a less skilled die-sinker; the other, Zorita 75, appears to be an imitation of the *Inclitus Rex* type. The coins have little in common with each other and may well be products of minor or unofficial workshops. The fineness is 42% for Zorita 75 and 74% for Zorita 80. The weights are also low, with 0.80 g for Zorita 75 and 0.97 g for Zorita 80, resulting in intrinsic values of 0.34 g and 0.71 g, respectively.

JII 6

Tomasini's JII 6 group was defined on the basis of only five coins, all from the Zorita hoard (Zorita 19, 68, 69, 70, and 71). Zorita 19 has some differences in style (e.g., no epaulets), but the rest are close enough to make it very likely that they came from a single workshop. Two of them, Zorita 70 and 71, share the same obverse die. The measurements are presented in Appendix 3.7. The fineness is highly variable. The five coins average 64% fineness (range 56% to 81%) and 1.313 g (range 1.10 to 1.42 g) weight, resulting in an average intrinsic value of 0.83 g Au (range 0.78 to 0.89 g). The standard deviation of the fineness is quite large (10.2), suggesting they may have come from more than one mint or else a mint with poorly controlled production, perhaps a minor or unofficial mint that only sporadically produced batches of coins.

JII 7

Tomasini recognized that his JII 7 category, consisting of seven coins, was "sketchy and problematic"⁵⁶; it is not clear whether it represents one workshop or an agglomeration of some products of various minor mints. Two coins from Zorita (Zorita 84 and 85), both from the same dies, were included by Tomasini in this group (Appendix 3.8). The finenesses for these two coins are 69% and 68% and the weights are 1.074 and 1.140 grams, giving intrinsic values of 0.74 g and 0.78 g (average of 0.76 g) respectively. Only one other coin of this group has been analyzed, GNC 9866,⁵⁷ which has a similar fineness of 69% Au but weighs 1.37 g, resulting in a much higher intrinsic value of 0.94 g. The other four coins classed as JII 7 by Tomasini all have reported weights in the range of 1.41 to 1.48 g. The two Zorita coins are difficult to relate to the other JII 7 coins in style as well as in weight, and they may be a variant of category JII 2 instead. They share the low weights common in the JII groups from Zorita, whereas the other JII 7 coins all have a much higher weight standard.

Curru

Toward the end of his classification, Tomasini placed a series of types whose obverse legends are not interpretable as the names of either emperors in Constantinople or kings of the Visigoths. Instead, the legends have become abstract strings of letters, often nearly symmetrical on the left and right sides of the coin. Many of them start with the sequence CVRRV or some variation thereof, hence

56. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremisses*, 126.

57. Published as a coin of Leovigild by Amorós and Mata, *Catálogo*, no. 21.

the name of the series. These coins are struck on wide flans, generally from well-made dies. Based on stylistic connections, the evidence of the Zorita hoard, and the general trend toward increasingly loose spellings of the legends, this series clearly belongs to the period of Justin II.⁵⁸

Tomasini divided this large series, comprising sixty-one coins in his catalogue, into five types. Of these, C 1 with nineteen coins and C 2 with eight coins form one branch, evidently related to the JAN 2 and JAN 8 categories; C 3 with twenty-five coins⁵⁹ and C 4 with three coins form a second branch. C 5 with seven coins has some connections to both.

No C 1 or C 2 coins were found in the Zorita hoard, which suggests that their mint or mints may be located some distance away from the principal sources of the Zorita hoard. Seven C 1 coins have been analyzed previously⁶⁰; they average 94% Au fineness (range 92 to 96%) and 1.43 g in weight (range 1.38 to 1.46 g), for an average intrinsic value of 1.34 g Au (range 1.29 to 1.38, SD 0.033).⁶¹ Six of the eight C 2 coins in Tomasini's catalogue have also been measured previously.⁶² They are metrologically quite similar to the C 1 coins, which would fit with their stylistic connections and the possibility that they may be from the same geographical region. The six coins measured had a mean fineness of 93% (range 91 to 94%) and a mean weight of 1.38 g (range 1.22 to 1.47 g), resulting in an average intrinsic value of 1.29 g Au (range 1.15 to 1.38, SD 0.84).

The C 3 type (Pl. 30, 26) is of particular stylistic interest because it is very closely connected to coins struck in the names of Leovigild and his son Hermenegild, and also to the obverse type of the first coins of Leovigild to name the mint on the reverse. It is generally supposed, based on these stylistic connections as well as Reinhart's theory connecting major types to the locations where kings were reported to be active, that this type must have been minted at Toledo.⁶³ Three coins from the Zorita hoard (Zorita 76, 78, and 79) are of the C 3 group (Appendix 3.9a). They have a mean fineness of 87% Au (range 83 to 89%) and a mean weight of 1.20 g (range 1.12 to 1.25 g), resulting in a mean intrinsic value of 1.04 g Au (0.99 to 1.10 g Au, SD 0.052). For the C 3 type as a whole, 24 coins

58. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremissis*, 126.

59. A die study in progress by the lead author includes more than fifty C 3 coins, indicating that it may be the most abundant type of the Visigothic pseudo-imperial series.

60. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 390–91, with six coins, plus one additional coin from the collection of Robert Hoge with a weight of 1.21 g and a fineness of 92% Au as measured by XRF.

61. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 390–91.

62. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 390–91.

63. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremissis*, 156; Grierson and Blackburn, *MEC* 1, 49.

have been analyzed (Appendix 3.9a and 3.9b),⁶⁴ averaging 91% Au in fineness (range 82 to 96%, SD 4.06) and 1.28 g in weight (range 1.02 to 1.41, SD 0.10), for a mean intrinsic value of 1.16 g Au (0.84 to 1.35 g Au, SD 0.12).

The three Zorita coins are slightly lower in mean fineness (87% versus 91%) and weight (1.20 versus 1.28 g) than the C 3 group overall, resulting in a 10% lower mean intrinsic value (1.04 versus 1.16 g Au). This difference is enough to be significant if they were from the same mint, especially if that mint was Toledo, where we would expect relatively close control over the quality of minting. However, the lower average is entirely due to Zorita 76 (Pl. 30, 27), whose style shows some differences from more typical C 3 coins. One of the notable differences is in the formation of the letters; a bar-shaped punch was used to make the ends of the letters on Zorita 76, unlike the triangle punch used on most C 3 coins.

Other C 3 coins are known with clumsy legends, crude engraving, and lower intrinsic values, pointing to a larger pattern (see, e.g., PB 15B in Appendix 3.9b and Pl. 30, 28, with a weight of 1.02 g and fineness of 82%). In general, the standard deviation of 0.10 for the intrinsic value of the twenty-four C 3 coins is four times greater than that of the Calle Cuna hoard (and also higher than that for the later Facing Bust series from Toledo),⁶⁵ which could indicate that some C 3 coins were minted at places other than the principal mint for the type, and that the production of these coins was not as well controlled.

C 4 is a very small group (only three examples in Tomasini's catalogue) that is related to C 3 but somewhat simplified in design. One Zorita coin (Zorita 77) is classed in this group. Zorita 77 has a fineness of 62% Au and a weight of 1.32 g, for an intrinsic value of 0.82 g Au. This is close to the other two C 4 coins that have been measured previously, which have an average fineness of 67% Au and weight of 1.30 g, for an intrinsic value of 0.86 g Au.⁶⁶ The weights for the C 4 group are in line with C 3, but the fineness is much lower, resulting in low intrinsic values similar to some of the III types.

C 5 is a small group (seven examples in Tomasini's catalogue) that is related to C 2 but also to the earlier JAN 4 type. One coin from the Zorita hoard (Zorita 73) is classed in this type. It has a fineness of 92% and a weight of 1.04 g, giving it an intrinsic value of 0.95 g Au. This is lower than the five C 5 coins measured

64. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 390–91, includes nineteen C 3 coins to which the three from Zorita and two others are now added, giving a total of twenty-four examples presented in Appendix 3.9.

65. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 394–401.

66. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 392–93.

previously,⁶⁷ which have a mean fineness of 94% and weight of 1.40 g, for an intrinsic value of 1.32 g Au. The Zorita coin resembles the rest of the C 5 group in fineness, but its weight is much lower, resulting in the low intrinsic value.

Inclitus Rex

The last three coins listed in the Zorita hoard—Zorita 88, 89 (Pl. 30, 29), and 90—are among the coins that Tomasini placed at the end of his sequence. These are coins on which the Visigothic king Leovigild's name replaced that of the Byzantine emperor on the obverse. They are generally similar in style to the C 3 type except that they have intelligible legends that approximate LIVVIGILDVS on the obverse and REX INCLITVS on the reverse. It is from the reverse legend that Tomasini called this group "Inclitus Rex" or "IR". Based on the close stylistic connection, the IR type is generally considered the direct successor of the C 3 type and, based on the same reasoning about "capital" cities, it is therefore generally thought to have been minted at Toledo, although Tomasini proposed that it may have been produced by multiple mints.⁶⁸ It is a major type, with twenty-eight examples in Tomasini's catalogue.⁶⁹

Zorita 88 and 89 have finenesses of 73% and 77% Au and weights of 1.262 and 1.288 grams, giving them intrinsic values of 0.92 g and 0.99 g Au respectively. Thus, they contain less gold than the mean of 1.16 g for the sample of twenty-four C 3 coins. Zorita 90 is a contemporary counterfeit of base metal. It was described by Cabré as gold-plated copper ("cobre chapado de oro");⁷⁰ it has crumbled into fragments since 1946. Cabré interpreted the legends to read DN+VNV+N+ on the obverse and RE+ INCT on the reverse,⁷¹ but the published photographs are not clear and the coin itself is no longer readable. Tomasini placed it in his IR group based on Cabré's reading and the stylistic attributes that could be seen of the types.⁷² A copy of the IR coinage would seem to indicate that the type had been in circulation for enough time to have been noted and copied by counterfeiters, suggesting that it should have begun some time before the presumed closing of the hoard in 578.

In addition to the two Zorita coins, eight other IR coins in the name of Leo-

67. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 392–93.

68. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremissis*, 146–48, 166, 170.

69. A preliminary die study by the lead author has identified fewer than fifty examples, suggesting that the mintage may have been slightly less than for the C 3 and JII 5 types. Pliego, *Moneda visigoda*, lists forty examples, and at least three more have appeared since then.

70. Cabré, *Tesorillo*, 15.

71. Cabré, *Tesorillo*, 15.

72. Tomasini, *Barbaric Tremissis*, 252.

vigild were previously analyzed,⁷³ and one additional one has been analyzed for this article. All eleven coins are presented in Appendix 3.12. They have a mean fineness of 76% Au (range 70 to 86%, SD 4.7) and a mean weight of 1.32 g (range 1.26 to 1.51 g), for a mean intrinsic value of 1.00 g of Au (range 0.90 to 1.16, SD 0.079). This represents a 14% reduction compared to the 1.16 g Au for the sample of twenty-four C 3 coins. Leovigild's IR coinage appears to have aimed at a weight standard of 1.30 g and a fineness of 75% (18 carats).

The *Inclitus Rex* category is believed to have been the latest of the types represented in the Zorita hoard, which makes its presence there important to dating the sequences of changes. The type is also important because very similar coins are known with the name of Hermenegild, Leovigild's oldest son. Leovigild appointed his sons as junior co-rulers around 573, but in 579 Hermenegild revolted against his father.⁷⁴ Hermenegild was based in Seville, which is most likely where his coins were minted.

Hermenegild

Few genuine coins are known with the name of Hermenegild, none from the Zorita hoard; Tomasini catalogued seven coins in all, but he noted that three of them were modern forgeries. Pliego's corpus has six or seven authentic coins: four with an *Inclitus Rex* reverse legend (Tomasini's type H 2), as well as two or three with a reverse legend reading *REGI A DEO VITA* (Tomasini's type H 3).⁷⁵ Two of those four H 2 coins have had their specific gravity measured previously,⁷⁶ and they are presented in Appendix 3.12c along with two specimens that have appeared recently.⁷⁷ These four H 2 coins have a mean fineness of 81% Au and a mean weight of 1.30 g, for an intrinsic value of 1.05 g Au. This is slightly higher than the 0.98 g Au for the IR coins of Leovigild. The greater intrinsic value of the H 2 coins is due primarily to the higher mean fineness of 81% compared to 76% for the IR coins of Leovigild. The few Hermenegild coins that have been measured fall in a tighter range of fineness (78% to 83% Au) compared to the IR coins of Leovigild (70 to 86% Au). One coin of the H 3 type with the reverse reading *REGI A DEO VITA* in the British Museum has also been measured. It has a

73. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 392–93.

74. Ioh. Biclar., *Chron.* 27, 54.

75. Pliego, *Moneda visigoda*, types 62 and 61. One uncertain coin is known only from verbal descriptions.

76. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 392–93.

77. R. Pliego, "La moneda visigoda: Anexo I," *Spal* 21 (2012): no. 62b.2; J. A. Herrero, 7 May 2015, lot 219.

fineness of 87% Au and a weight of 1.27 g, giving an intrinsic value of 1.10 g Au. This is similar to the other (H 2) coins of Hermenegild. The H 3 type most likely came toward the end of Hermenegild's revolt, which was suppressed in 584.

The proposed burial date for the Zorita hoard of 578–79 most likely predates the revolt of Hermenegild in Seville, so the change to placing the name of Leovigild on the coinage must predate the coinage of Hermenegild. The IR coinage itself must have begun somewhat earlier, if it was already being counterfeited before the Zorita hoard closed, and it was still current when Hermenegild began issuing his own coins. A hoard representing Leovigild's next revision of the coinage provides additional evidence for the date of the IR coinage.⁷⁸ A group of twenty gold *tremisses* found in an excavation in Mérida includes nineteen with profile bust and the king's name on the obverse and a cross on steps with a mint name on the reverse. The remaining coin also has the cross-on-steps reverse type, but it retains a reverse legend of the Inclitus Rex type. Because the hoard contains six coins combining Leovigild's name with the mint name Emerita, the hoard must date after Leovigild's conquest of the city in 582. No coins with a Victory reverse type were present in this hoard, so the hoard appears to have been composed of fairly new coins. The transition from the IR type to the Cross-on-Steps type may, therefore, have occurred around 582 or shortly before.

A further mystery is the very close stylistic similarity between C 3, IR, H 2, and H 3, if they were the products of two separate major mints, Toledo and Seville. There could be an unknown explanation, such as an engraver originally at Toledo who went to Seville with Hermenegild, but further study is needed.

Other Coins from the Zorita Hoard

The coins Zorita 1 to Zorita 8 were considered not to be Visigothic by Cabré or other authors. Knowing where these coins were produced would give some idea of the directions from which coins entered the hoard. Of the eight, Zorita 5 is a coin of Justin II from the Byzantine province of Spania, a series not yet recognized when Cabré first published the hoard. Three other coins of Justin II from Spania are known (Appendix 3.13a); the four have an average fineness of 87% and weight of 1.33 grams, for an average intrinsic value of 1.15 grams of gold.⁷⁹ The study of the coins of Byzantine Spania indicated that they were minted at a value close to that of the Visigoths, with whom the province had a long and very

78. P. Mateos Cruz, A. Pizzo, and R. Pliego, "Un tesoro de tremises visigodos hallado en el llamado «Forum Provincial» de Augusta Emerita," *Archivo Español de Arqueología* 78 (2005): 251–70.

79. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 380–81. Note that Zorita 5 was re-measured under better conditions for this article, yielding a somewhat lower measurement than before.

loosely controlled border. In particular, the intrinsic values of these Byzantine coins are similar to some specific Visigothic types, namely JAN 5, JII 4 without Leovigild's name, and JII 5 types I and II, all of which may have been minted during the reign of Justin II. However, they are higher than some of the other JII groups such as JII 2 and JII 3. It seems reasonable to suppose that at a time when the Visigothic standards varied, the Byzantines in Spania followed the standard of a major mint near their territory in the southeast; following this hypothesis would suggest that one or more of the similar groups came from an area adjoining the southeastern coast that was under Byzantine rule.

Zorita 7 is a Suevic *tremissis* of the Latina Munita type. It is mentioned but not included in the catalogue of the definitive study of Suevic coins by Cabral and Metcalf.⁸⁰ It is not from any of the dies in their catalogue but is similar to some in the group of miscellaneous Latina Munita *tremisses*.⁸¹ The Latina Munita series is believed to have been minted in the areas north of the Minho River during the decade or so before Leovigild conquered the Suevian kingdom in 585. Many coins have legends that can be recognized as referring to cities, presumably mints, including Bergidum and León. Cabral and Metcalf, using a surface method (PIXE), reported the average fineness for five coins in the Miscellaneous Latina Munita group as 71.4%, with a range of 61.8% to 83.1%.⁸² The specific gravity of Zorita 7 was found to be 14.18, corresponding to a fineness of 56%, giving it an intrinsic value of 0.52 g Au. Considering that surface methods such as PIXE can give results around 10% higher than specific gravity,⁸³ this would place Zorita 7 within the range of the coins reported by Cabral and Metcalf. Other Latina Munita coins for which specific gravity measurements are known include MEC 1.293 with a weight of 1.22 g and a fineness of 59%, resulting in an intrinsic value of 0.72 g Au, and ANS 2014.44.8 with a weight of 1.12 g and a fineness of 46%, resulting in an intrinsic value of 0.51 g Au (Appendix 3.13b). Both of these coins are damaged at the edge (the missing portion is around 1.5% of MEC 1.293 and 3% of ANS 2014.44.8); if the weight is corrected for this, the intrinsic values would be 0.73 g and 0.53 g, respectively. These three Suevic coins are lower in intrinsic value (average 0.59 g) than any of the main JII groups, suggesting that economic connections between the Visigothic and Suevian kingdoms may have been very limited.

80. J. M. P. Cabral and D. M. Metcalf, *A moeda sueva / Suevic Coinage* (Porto: Sociedade Portuguesa de Numismática, 1997).

81. Cabral and Metcalf, *Moeda sueva*, plate 20.

82. Cabral and Metcalf, *Moeda sueva*, 176–77, 312.

83. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 355.

A particular group of late Suevic coins that may be especially relevant to Visigothic metrology, although not represented in the Zorita hoard, consists of those with the obverse legend *LATINA EMERI MVNITA* or similar. Whether these coins should be associated with Emerita Augusta (Mérida) has been the subject of considerable debate. Although the dies for these coins appear to have been made by the same engraver as Latina Munita coins associated with Bergidum in northwestern Spain, it has been suggested that the EMERI coins were made for use in Mérida during Hermenegild's revolt, when the Suevian king Miro intervened in the conflict.⁸⁴ Weight and fineness have been measured for three coins of this group, one by PIXE and two by specific gravity (Appendix 3.13c). These coins are higher in intrinsic value (average 0.80 g) than the other Latina Munita coins, and may follow a Visigothic standard of that time rather than the standard used in Gallaecia north of the Minho.⁸⁵

Six other coins in the Zorita hoard have been attributed, at one time or another, to Merovingian Gaul. Two of them (Zorita 6 and 8) are of the Visigothic reverse type with Victory holding palm branch and wreath, but in a somewhat irregular style. Zorita 6 has a Merovingian-style "boucle perdue" on the obverse, but it is otherwise entirely Visigothic in types and technique, even though it does not correspond to any of Tomasini's major stylistic categories (Appendix 3.13d). Zorita 8 is also entirely Visigothic in types and technique except that the obverse bust lacks a pectoral cross. This coin has been included in Tomasini's JII 2b category above.

This leaves four other coins (Zorita 1–4) whose reverse types do not conform to the Victory with Palm and Wreath used for all Visigothic *tremisses* from the time of Anastasius to Leovigild's introduction of the Cross-on-Steps reverse, ca. 582. Two of these coins (Zorita 3 and 4) have a Victory facing, holding crown and orb, on the reverse. This standard Byzantine type was imitated by the Lombards as well as the Franks. The simplified rendering of Victory on Zorita 3 and 4 is very similar to some Merovingian coins, but the obverse busts, although crudely engraved, would be more typical for Visigothic coins, apart from the lack

84. According to Gregory of Tours (*Hist.* 6.43), Miro intervened on behalf of Hermenegild; the account by John of Biclarum (*Chron.* 65) is unclear and can be read to indicate that he intervened either on behalf of Leovigild or on behalf of Hermenegild. In any case, Mérida seems to have been involved in the conflict (Greg. Tur. *Hist.* 6.18).

85. Cabral and Metcalf, *Moeda sueva*, 91, 177. They noted that the one *LATINA EMERI MVNITA* coin they analyzed was of "exceptionally high percentage of gold (86%)" compared to the other eight coins of Bergidum style they measured. They suggested that the EMERI coins were struck on a different standard similar to the Suevic *tremisses* in the name of Valentinian III with an inverted R on the reverse.

of a pectoral cross. As for technique, both coins are struck on wide, thin flans (18–19 mm) and the dies for both show some use of punches. In the 570s, both of these technical characteristics were standard for Visigothic coins but unusual in Merovingian coins.

The last two coins in this group (Zorita 1 and 2) were struck from the same pair of dies. The types and legends are in no way like any known Visigothic coins. The legends are, however, normal for Merovingian coins, specifying a moneyer named Daumeris and a location called Vasatis.⁸⁶ The reverse type, depicting a man seated to right and holding a staff, also has some parallels in Merovingian coins from southwestern France.⁸⁷ The technical characteristics, once again, are unusual, though. Both coins are struck on wide, thin flans (18–19 mm) and the legends show some use of punches.

This combination of Visigothic technical characteristics with Merovingian style suggests some sort of unofficial issue. Perhaps a Spanish moneyer or moneyers, seeking to mint some gold on a private basis and perhaps evade legal restrictions or fiscal obligations, chose to make dies imitating Merovingian coins? This seems the most likely explanation for Zorita 1 through 4.

These four coins (Appendix 3.13e) have a mean fineness of 65% (range 62% to 67%) and mean weight of 1.44 g (range 1.40 to 1.48 g), resulting in a mean intrinsic value of 0.94 g (range 0.91 to 0.96 g) with a standard deviation of 0.029. Thus, despite the stylistic range, this is a homogeneous group in its intrinsic value, and even more so when Zorita 1 and 2 are separated from Zorita 3 and 4: Zorita 1 and 2 both have an intrinsic value of 0.96 g, and Zorita 3 and 4 both have an intrinsic value of 0.91 g. The values are similar to some of the large groups of JII coins of low values in the Zorita hoard, which might indicate a regional relationship.

86. This is thought to refer to Bazas (Gironde) in southwestern France: A. de Belfort, *Description générale des monnaies mérovingiennes*, vol. 3 (Paris: Société Française de Numismatique, 1893), 375–76. However, this moneyer is otherwise unknown and this reverse type is not otherwise known for Bazas.

87. E.g., Belfort, *Description*, vol. 2, no. 2077.

DISCUSSION

In the second quarter of the sixth century the *tremisses* issued by the Visigoths were of intrinsic value close to the Byzantine standard, with little variation within or between the different Tomasini types, as shown by the Calle Cuna hoard. However, during the third quarter of the sixth century Visigothic *tremisses* became highly variable in value both between and within the Tomasini types, and this is particularly true for the ones he attributed to the time of Justin II.

Cabré, in his monograph on the Zorita hoard, reported the fineness that he estimated based on color; he described a third of the Zorita coins as being of “oro bajo” or “oro muy bajo.”⁸⁸ Although Tomasini included Cabré’s observations in his catalogue and discussed them in his work, the existence of pseudo-imperial coins of fineness below 80% has been rarely noted in publications since Tomasini, and the few that have been found have often been questioned as counterfeits.⁸⁹ This may be because Cabré’s terms are relative and no quantitative measurements of fineness have been made of the Zorita coins until now. In fact, Cabré’s descriptions are not very accurate; many of his “oro de ley” coins are of low fineness, and others said to be of “oro bajo” are not.⁹⁰ The fact that the few previous measurements of Visigothic coins in the name of Justin II have not uncovered coins of very low fineness raises the question of whether the Zorita hoard is representative of the whole kingdom. Answering this question will depend on finding more coins of the same date, especially of Tomasini’s JII types.

There is clear indication of a debasement between ca. 550 and ca. 565 during the reign of Athanagild, which can be seen by comparison of the coins in the name of Justinian from Calle Cuna, from general collections, and from Zorita. The JAN 2 type must have been from an important mint, and the Zorita examples are some 36% lower in gold than the ones from Calle Cuna a generation

88. Cabré, *Tesorillo*.

89. See, e.g., Grierson and Blackburn, *MEC 1*, no. 201, with a fineness of 74%. It is the only pseudo-imperial Visigothic coin below 85% in the Fitzwilliam collection and comes with a note, “The low weight and fineness support Tomasini’s view, based on style, that the piece is irregular, though not a modern forgery.” Likewise, in Metcalf et al., “Sixth-Century Visigothic Metrology,” the only coin with a fineness below 85% was one in the name of Justin I with 78% gold, for which the authors noted, “The gold content suggests a contemporary copy.” M. Marques Gomes, J. M. Peixoto Cabral, and J. Rodrigues Marinho. *Ensaio sobre história monetária da monarquia visigoda* (Porto: Sociedade Portuguesa de Numismática, 1995), found no coins below 79% (no. 12, JAN 3). Metcalf and Schweizer, “Milliprobe Analyses,” found no coins below 86% (no. O.173, unclassified). Bartlett et al., “Spania,” found only one pseudo-imperial coin below 80% (a JII 7 of 69% Au) apart from the C 4 and IR series.

90. Compare Appendix 2 and Appendix 3.

Figure 2. Average intrinsic value (gold content) of major categories discussed in this article, with error bar showing one standard deviation above mean. Asterisk indicates small samples (one or two coins) for which standard deviation is not shown.

earlier. The JAN 5 type, evidently another important mint, is not present in the Calle Cuna hoard, but the examples from Zorita are 26% lower in gold than other known JAN 5 coins, suggesting a similar debasement.

For the types in the name of Justin II the story is more complicated because they overlap the reign of Athanagild as well as Liuva I and Leovigild. From Figure 2, it can be seen that JII 2, JII 3, JII 6, and JII 7 are all low in value, close to the JAN 2 and JAN 5 coins from Zorita, which are believed to be late examples of their types. The other major groups—JII 4 and JII 5 (not present in the Zorita hoard), as well as the probably contemporary Curru groups—have a higher intrinsic value. This suggests an attempt to reform the coinage, probably early in the reign of Leovigild, that was only applied effectively at a few major mints, while others produced more debased coins.

The Curru groups are the largest series that indicates an attempt to reform the coinage to near the standards of the Calle Cuna hoard. C 1 and C 2, with a fine-

ness of 94%, are very close to the average 95% fineness for the Calle Cuna coins. With mean weights of 1.41 and 1.42 g, C 1 and C 2 are only slightly lighter than the 1.45 g for Calle Cuna, resulting in an average intrinsic value of 1.34 g for C 1 and 1.29 g for C 2, compared to 1.38 g for Calle Cuna. However, C 3, the most abundant Curru type, although it has a fineness that is only slightly lower (91%), appears to have adopted a weight standard of 1.30 g, so the resulting intrinsic value is considerably less than that of the Calle Cuna coins, at 1.16 g Au.

The differences in standards between the Curru groups, along with the variation within the C 3 group itself and the continued minting of low-fineness JII coins, point to the limited effectiveness of this reform. A second reform may have been attempted, marked by the clear placement of the name of Leovigild on the IR, JII 4, and JII 5 coins among others. This placement of the king's name would clearly distinguish the new coins from previous ones otherwise indistinguishable in style and could also have been ordered if new standards were to be established throughout the kingdom, such as the usage of the weight standard of 1.30 g.

If such a reform occurred at the same time throughout the kingdom, the JII 4 coins with the name of Leovigild, JII 5 type III also with the name of Leovigild, and Inclitus Rex would represent the change at three important mints. However, while the JII 4 coins with the name of Leovigild and the IR coins are very close to each other in value (0.97 and 1.00 g Au), JII 5 type III is some 15% higher than those in intrinsic value. Therefore, we cannot be sure that the placement of Leovigild's name occurred simultaneously and used the same standards at all mints.

It appears that a complete unification of standards in the kingdom may not have occurred until the next typological change to the Cross-on-Steps series, in which the weight standard of 1.30 g and the lower fineness of 75% were adopted throughout the realm, resulting in an intrinsic value of 0.975 g—in line with the previous JII 4 and IR values, but not with the other coins of the 570s.⁹¹ In the final reform of Leovigild, the designs changed to facing busts on both obverse and reverse, and the weight standard was increased to around 1.50 g while the fineness stayed at 75% (18 karat), for an intrinsic value of 1.125 g of gold.⁹²

91. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 394.

92. Bartlett et al., "Spania," 394–95.

Table 1. Summary of changes in standard with the introduction of Leovigild's name

	Weight	Fineness	Intrinsic value
JII 4 meaningless legends	1.36	92	1.25
JII 4 name of Leovigild	1.27	75	0.97 (22% reduction)
JII 5 type II name of Justin	1.47	93	1.37
JII 5 type III name of Leovigild	1.33	87	1.16 (15% reduction)
C 3	1.28	91	1.16
IR Leovigild	1.32	76	1.00 (14% reduction)

Some of the JII groups have a low average intrinsic value and a large standard deviation, which would seem to indicate that mints were having serious difficulty in producing coins at the standards that had been used before 550. The substantial variability indicates poor control over the minting process. Many of the types also encompass considerable stylistic variation, and Tomasini has a number of small subtypes that are difficult to relate to the main groups. This may point to the existence of significant amounts of coining on an unofficial basis. Difficulty maintaining standards, poor control of minting, and widespread unofficial minting might all be indicators of significant economic or political problems in the kingdom.

To understand the significant changes in the value of the coinage during the later part of Justinian I's reign and that of Justin II, an examination of the very scanty historical record for the period 550 to 578 is important. The period between 548 and 555 was dramatic, with the murder of three kings, loss of life and royal treasure during Agila's attempt to recover control of Córdoba, a protracted civil war between Agila (then established in Mérida) and Athanagild (in Seville), and a Byzantine intervention resulting in occupation of the southeastern coast. The upheaval ended with Agila's death in 554, after which Athanagild ruled the kingdom until his death in 568.

The reign of Athanagild is the least documented of any period in the history of the Visigoths in Iberia.⁹³ Isidore's *Historia Gothorum* skips directly from the death of Agila in 554 (HG 47) to Athanagild's death in 567 (HG 48), with only a brief mention of the Byzantine intervention for Athanagild's reign. The chronicle of John of Biclarum does not begin until 568. It is telling that after Athanagild's death in Toledo there was an interregnum of five months before a new king was selected, and the result was a king, Liuva I, based in the distant

93. Cf. R. Collins, *Visigothic Spain* (Oxford: Blackwell, 2004), 52.

province of Gallia Narbonensis. This in itself suggests that the political situation in central Hispania may have been in disarray. A second indication that there may have been problems in Hispania in the reign of Athanagild is found in John of Biclarum's narrative of the early years of Leovigild's reign, when year after year Leovigild made military campaigns throughout the peninsula to restore control over areas where control had been lost, as well as new areas.⁹⁴

Therefore, there are indications of political and economic instability in Hispania during the later years of Justinian I and the reign of Justin II. This instability may have resulted in lack of careful control—sometimes lack of any royal control—over mints in some parts of Hispania, enabling the minting of variably debased coins at different mints, as shown by the results of this study. The numismatic evidence for this period is largely dominated by the large hoard from Zorita, and until more finds from other areas are known, it cannot be determined how widespread the debasement was, nor any regional variation in the chronology of debasement and reform.

Under Leovigild several reforms were made that finally resulted in a uniform coinage. In addition to the restoration of centralized control, it is possible that the addition of gold to the treasury through successful campaigning may have had a role as well. The final reform produced a coinage that was lower in intrinsic value than the coinage before 550 but uniform throughout the kingdom.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank the numerous individuals who have allowed the lead author to measure coins in their care, especially A. Navarro, director of the Archaeological Museum of Seville, for access to the Calle Cuna hoard; Paloma Otero of the Museo Arqueológico Nacional in Madrid, for access to the Zorita hoard as well as other specimens; Albert Estrada Rius and Maria Clua Mercadal of the Gabinet Numismàtic de Catalunya, Museu Nacional d'Art de Catalunya, Barcelona; and Elena Stoliarik and Robert Hoge at the American Numismatic Society. We also would like to thank Lauris Olson for having made his unpublished specific gravity measurements available to researchers.

94. L. García Moreno, *Leovigildo: Unidad y diversidad de un reinado* (Madrid: Real Academia de la Historia, 2008), 33, has suggested, based on a line in the *Consularia Caesaraugustana*, that in the South even Seville, in addition to Córdoba, may have been in revolt during part of Athanagild's reign.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Amorós, J., and A. Mata Berruezo. *Catálogo de las monedas visigodas del Gabinete Numismático de Cataluña*. Barcelona: Ayuntamiento de Barcelona, 1952.
- Barceló, M. “Monedas visigodas de Hispania: Un estado de la cuestión y algunos problemas de metrología y organización de las emisiones monetarias.” *Numisma* 147 (1977): 55–80.
- Barral i Altet, X. *La circulation des monnaies suèves et visigothiques*. München: Artemis, 1976.
- Bartlett, P., A. Oddy, and C. Morrisson. “The Byzantine Gold Coinage of *Spania* (Justinian I to Heraclius).” *Revue numismatique* 167 (2011): 351–401.
- Belfort, A. de. *Description générale des monnaies mérovingiennes*. Paris: Société Française de Numismatique, 1892–95.
- Cabral, J. M. Peixoto, and D. M. Metcalf. *A moeda sueva / Suevic Coinage*. Porto: Sociedade Portuguesa de Numismática, 1997.
- Cabré Aguiló, J. *El tesorillo visigodo de trientes de las excavaciones del Plan Nacional de 1944–45 en Zorita de los Canes (Guadalajara)*. Madrid: Ministerio de Educación Nacional, 1946.
- Castro Priego, M. “*Reccopolis* y los contextos numismáticos de época visigoda en el centro de la Península Ibérica.” *Revue numismatique* 171 (2014): 463–495.
- Collins, R. *Visigothic Spain, 409–711*. Oxford: Blackwell, 2004.
- Crusafont, M., J. Benages, and J. Noguera. “Silver Visigothic Coinage.” *Numismatic Chronicle* 176 (2016): 241–260.
- Fossella, J. “‘Waiting Only for a Pretext’: A New Chronology for the Sixth-Century Byzantine Invasion of Spain.” *Estudios Bizantinos* 1 (2013): 30–38.
- García Moreno, L. *Leovigildo: Unidad y diversidad de un reinado*. Madrid: Real Academia de la Historia, 2008.
- Geneviève, V. “Découverte de deux *tremisses* visigothiques.” In *D’Iluro à Oloron-Sainte-Marie*, edited by D. Barraud and F. Réchin, 383–396. Pessac: Fédération Aquitania, 2013.
- Greg. Tur. = Gregory of Tours, *Libri Historiarum X*, ed. B. Krusch and W. Levison. *Monumenta Germaniae Historica, Scriptorum Rerum Merovingicarum* 1.1, rev. ed. Hannover: Hahn, 1951.
- Grierson, P., and M. Blackburn. *Medieval European Coinage 1: The Early Middle Ages (5th–10th Centuries)*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1986.
- Ioh. Biclár. = Iohannes Biclarensis, *Chronicon*, in *Victoris Tunnunensis Chronicon cum Reliquiis ex Consularibus Caesaraugustanis et Iohannis Biclarensis Chronicon*, edited by C. Cardelle de Hartmann. *Corpus Christianorum, series latina* 173A. Turnhout: Brepols, 2001.

- Jonson, T., M. Blet-Lemarquand, and C. Morrisson. "The Byzantine Mint in Carthage and the Islamic Mint in North Africa: New Metallurgical Findings." *Revue numismatique* 171 (2014): 655–699.
- Kent, J. P. C. *The Roman Imperial Coinage X*. London: Spink and Son, 1994.
- Kurt, A. *Minting, State and Economy in the Visigothic Kingdom: From Settlement in Aquitaine through the First Decade of the Muslim Conquest of Spain*. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, in press.
- Le Gentilhomme, P. "Le monnayage et la circulation monétaire dans les royaumes barbares en Occident (V^e–VIII^e siècle)." *Revue numismatique* 7 (1943): 46–112, 8 (1944–45): 13–59.
- Marques, M. Gomes, J. M. Peixoto Cabral, and J. Rodrigues Marinho. 1995. *Ensaio sobre história monetária da monarquia visigoda*. Porto: Sociedade Portuguesa de Numismática.
- Mateos, P., A. Pizzo, and R. Pliego. "Un tesoro de tremises visigodos hallado en el llamado «Foro Provincial» de Augusta Emerita." *Archivo Español de Arqueología* 78 (2005): 251–270.
- Mateu y Llopis, F. *Catálogo de las monedas previsigodas y visigodas del Gabinete Numismático del Museo Arqueológico Nacional*. Madrid: Cuerpo Facultativo de Archiveros, Bibliotecarios y Arqueólogos, 1936.
- Metcalf, D. M., J. M. P. Cabral, and L. C. Alves. "Sixth-Century Visigothic Metrology: Some Evidence from Portugal." *American Journal of Numismatics* 3–4 (1991–92): 65–90.
- Metcalf, D. M., and F. Schweizer. "Milliprobe Analyses of Some Visigothic, Suevic, and Other Gold Coins of the Early Middle Ages." *Archaeometry* 12 (1970): 173–187.
- Miles, G. C. *The Coinage of the Visigoths of Spain, Leovigild to Achila II*. Hispanic Numismatic Series 2. New York: American Numismatic Society, 1952.
- Olmo Enciso, L., ed. *Recópolis y la ciudad en la época visigoda*. Zona Arqueológica 9. Alcalá de Henares: Museo Arqueológico Regional, 2008.
- Pliego Vázquez, R. *La moneda visigoda*. Sevilla: Universidad de Sevilla, 2009.
- . "La moneda visigoda: Anexo I." *Spal* 21 (2012): 209–231.
- . "A Hoard of Late Roman and Visigothic Gold." *Numismatic Chronicle* 176 (2016): 377–386.
- Reinhart, W. "Die Münzen des westgotischen Reiches von Toledo." *Deutsches Jahrbuch für Numismatik* 3–4 (1940–41): 66–101.
- Tomasini, W. J. *The Barbaric Tremissis in Spain and Southern France, Anastasius to Leovigild*. Numismatic Notes and Monographs 152. New York: American Numismatic Society, 1964.

Vico Monteoliva, J., M. C. Cores Gomendio, and G. Cores Uría. *Corpus nummorum visigothorum, ca. 575–714, Leovigildus–Achila*. Madrid: J. Vico, 2006.

Yoon, D. “Evolution of Stylistic Patterns in Pre-Visigothic Tremisses.” Paper presented at the XV International Numismatic Congress, Taormina, Italy, 2015.

LIST OF ILLUSTRATIONS

1. Calle Cuna hoard, Tomasini type JI 1 (Pliego no. 50).
2. Calle Cuna hoard, Tomasini type JAN 3 (Pliego no. 66).
3. Calle Cuna hoard, Tomasini type JAN 2 (Pliego no. 75).
4. Calle Cuna hoard, Tomasini type JAN 2 (Pliego no. 74).
5. Calle Cuna hoard, Tomasini type JAN 8 (Pliego no. 73).
6. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JAN 2 (Zorita 23).
7. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JAN 2 (Zorita 21).
8. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JAN 2b (Zorita 26).
9. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JAN 5 (Zorita 18).
10. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JAN 5 (Zorita 15).
11. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JII 2 (Zorita 40).
12. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JII 2 (Zorita 41).
13. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JII 2 (Zorita 43).
14. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JII 2 (Zorita 50).
15. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JII 2 (Zorita 51).
16. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JII 2a (Zorita 45).
17. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JII 3 (Zorita 53).
18. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JII 3 (Zorita 33).
19. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JII 3 (Zorita 62).
20. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JII 3 (Zorita 59).
21. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type JII 4, nonsense legend (Zorita 87).
22. Tomasini type JII 4, Leovigild legend (ANS 2015.48.1).
23. Tomasini type JII 5, type I (ANS 2014.45.44).
24. Tomasini type JII 5, type II (Ashmolean Museum).
25. Tomasini type JII 5, type III (Museo Arqueológico Nacional, Madrid, no. 105318).
26. Tomasini type C 3 (ANS 2014.45.55).
27. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type C 3 (Zorita 76).
28. Tomasini type C 3 (PB 15b).
29. Zorita hoard, Tomasini type IR (Zorita 89).

APPENDIX 1

The two tables in this appendix present the weight, fineness, and intrinsic value of the Visigothic coins in the Calle Cuna hoard. All measurements were carried out by Peter Bartlett.

Appendix 1.1. Visigothic *solidi* from the Calle Cuna hoard

	Name on obv.	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Cross-ref.
Seville 8644	Anastasius	3.9870	19.18	99.2	3.95	Pliego no. 42
Seville 8645	Justin	4.2877	19.11	98.7	4.23	Pliego no. 44
Seville 8646	Justinian	4.3784	18.82	96.9	4.24	Pliego no. 52
Seville 8647	Justinian	4.3752	18.88	97.4	4.26	Pliego no. 53
Seville 8648	Justinian	4.4232	18.91	97.4	4.31	Pliego no. 54
Seville 8649	Justinian	4.4068	18.75	96.4	4.25	Pliego no. 55
Seville 8650	Justinian	4.4463	19.09	98.5	4.38	Pliego no. 56
Seville 8651	Justinian	4.4191	19.05	98.3	4.34	Pliego no. 57
Seville 8652	Justinian	4.4019	19.19	99.2	4.37	Pliego no. 58
Seville 8653	Justinian	4.4336	19.09	98.5	4.37	Pliego no. 59
Seville 8654	Justinian	4.4326	19.13	98.8	4.38	Pliego no. 60
Seville 8655	Justinian	4.4685	19.06	98.3	4.39	Pliego no. 61
Seville 8656	Justinian	4.4414	18.97	97.5	4.33	Pliego no. 62
Mean		4.377		98.1	4.29	
Standard deviation		0.126		0.89	0.12	

Appendix 1.2. Visigothic *tremisses* from the Calle Cuna hoard

	Name on obv.	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Cross-ref.
Seville 8657	Anastasius*	1.4615	18.77	96.5	1.41	Pliego no. 43
Seville 8658	Justin	1.4383	18.69	95.9	1.38	Pliego no. 48
Seville 8659	Justinian	1.4486	18.65	95.7	1.39	Pliego no. 63
Seville 8660	Justin	1.4429	18.37	93.7	1.35	Pliego no. 60
Seville 8661	Justinian	1.4468	18.50	94.6	1.37	Pliego no. 75
Seville 8662	Justinian	1.4479	18.59	95.2	1.38	Pliego no. 64
Seville 8663	Justinian	1.4095	18.62	95.4	1.35	Pliego no. 69
Seville 8664	Justinian	1.4496	18.54	94.9	1.38	Pliego no. 70
Seville 8665	Justinian	1.4477	18.85	97.1	1.41	Pliego no. 65
Seville 8666	Justinian	1.4635	18.83	96.9	1.42	Pliego no. 66
Seville 8667	Justin	1.4593	18.51	94.7	1.38	Pliego no. 45
Seville 8668	Justin	1.4393	18.97	97.7	1.41	Pliego no. 51
Seville 8669	Justinian	1.4379	18.40	94.0	1.35	Pliego no. 74
Seville 8670	Justin**	1.4238	18.41	94.1	1.34	Pliego no. 50
Seville 8671	Justinian	1.4570	18.53	94.8	1.38	Pliego no. 76
Seville 8672	Justinian	1.4532	18.43	94.2	1.37	Pliego no. 73
Seville 8673	Justinian	1.4586	18.94	97.5	1.42	Pliego no. 68
Seville 8674	Justinian	1.4467	18.55	95.0	1.37	Pliego no. 71
Seville 8675	Justinian	1.4633	18.76	96.4	1.41	Pliego no. 77
Seville 8676	Justin	1.4325	18.71	96.1	1.38	Pliego no. 49
Seville 8677	Justinian	1.4514	18.55	95.0	1.38	Pliego no. 72
Seville 8678	Justin	1.4451	18.43	94.2	1.36	Pliego no. 47
Seville 8679	Justinian	1.4327	18.33	93.5	1.34	Pliego no. 67
Mean		1.446		95.3	1.38	
Standard deviation		0.013		1.23	0.025	

* Name unclear; may be Justin.

** Name unclear; may be Justinian.

APPENDIX 2

This table presents an overview of the Zorita hoard according to the classifications of Cabré, Tomasini, and Barral, showing the diverse interpretations of the legends as well as the way Tomasini's classification differs in structure from those of Cabré and Barral. We have listed Cabré's weight for each piece, since these have been cited by various authors, for comparison with the weights as measured by Bartlett in Appendix 3. In addition, we have included Cabré's visual estimates of the fineness of the gold: "oro de ley" (gold of legal purity), "oro bajo" (base gold), "oro muy bajo" (very base gold), or "cobre chapado de oro" (copper plated with gold). In the last column is a cross-reference to the table in Appendix 3 giving the specific gravity analysis for each coin.

Cabré no.	Cabré category	Tomasini category	Tomasini no.	Barral category	Cabré weight	Cabré fineness	Analysis
1	Merovingia			Mérovigien	1.50	Oro de ley	App. 3.13e
2	Merovingia			Mérovigien	1.48	Oro de ley	App. 3.13e
3	Merovingia	Visigothic imitation of Byzantine		Mérovigien	1.58	Oro de ley	App. 3.13e
4	Merovingia	Visigothic imitation of Byzantine		Mérovigien	1.44	Oro de ley	App. 3.13e
5	Merovingia	Hispano-Byzantine		Byzantin d'Espagne?	1.15	Oro de ley	App. 3.13a
6	Merovingia	Unsorted	657	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.44	Oro de ley	App. 3.13d
7	Sueva	Suevian		Suève	1.00	Oro de ley	App. 3.13b
8	Visigoda ¿arbonense?	JII 2b	440	Mérovigien	1.40	Oro de ley	App. 3.3d
9	Visigoda ¿arbonense?	JII 2a	435	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.11	Oro de ley	App. 3.3c
10	Visigoda ¿arbonense?	JII 2b	439	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.48	Oro de ley	App. 3.3d
11	Visigoda ¿arbonense?	JII 2b	438	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.47	Oro de ley	App. 3.3d
12	Visigoda ¿arbonense?	JII 2a	436	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.24	Oro de ley	App. 3.3c
13	Justiniano I	JII 3	449	Légende de Justinien	1.04	Oro de ley	App. 3.4a
14	Justiniano I	JII 3	454	Légende de Justinien	1.46	Oro de ley	App. 3.4a

Cabré no.	Cabré category	Tomasini category	Tomasini no.	Barral category	Cabré weight	Cabré fineness	Analysis
15	Justiniano I	JAN 5	347	Légende de Justinien	1.44	Oro de ley	App. 3.2a
16	Justiniano I	JII 3	441	Légende de Justinien	1.46	Oro bajo	App. 3.4a
17	Justiniano I	JAN 5	346	Légende de Justinien	1.07	Oro de ley	App. 3.2a
18	Justiniano I	JAN 5	353	Légende de Justinien	1.07	Oro de ley	App. 3.2a
19	Justiniano I	JII 6	529	Légende de Justinien	1.16	Oro de ley	App. 3.7
20	Justiniano I	JAN 2	267	Légende de Justinien	1.34	Oro de ley	App. 3.1a
21	Justiniano I	JAN 2	272	Légende de Justinien	1.41	Oro de ley	App. 3.1a
22	Justiniano I	JAN 2	276	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.12	Oro de ley	App. 3.1a
23	Justiniano I	JAN 2	275	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.23	Oro de ley	App. 3.1a
24	Justiniano I	JAN 2	274	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.11	Oro de ley	App. 3.1a
25	Justiniano I	JAN 2	273	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.33	Oro de ley	App. 3.1a
26	Justiniano I	JAN 2b	290	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.34	Oro de ley	App. 3.1c
27	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JII 2	418	Légende de Justin II lisible	1.28	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
28	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JII 2	421	Légende de Justin II lisible	1.22	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
29	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JAN 5	354	Légende de Justin II lisible	1.15	Oro de ley	App. 3.2a

Cabré no.	Cabré category	Tomasini category	Tomasini no.	Barral category	Cabré weight	Cabré fineness	Analysis
30	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JII 2	419	Légende de Justin II lisible	1.17	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
31	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JII 2	413	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.11	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
32	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JII 2	429	Légende de Justin II lisible	1.31	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
33	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JII 3	462	Légende de Justin II lisible	1.41	Oro bajo	App. 3.4a
34	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JII 3	461	Légende de Justin II lisible	1.46	Oro bajo	App. 3.4a
35	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JII 3	463	Légende de Justin II lisible	1.40	Oro bajo	App. 3.4a
36	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JII 3	459	Légende de Justin II lisible	1.43	Oro muy bajo	App. 3.4a
37	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JII 2	412	Légende de Justin II lisible	1.20	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
38	Justino II, leyendas correctas	JII 2	420	Légende de Justin II? déformée	0.98	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
39	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3a	476	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.47	Oro bajo	App. 3.4c
40	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2	426	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.10	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
41	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2	425	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.38	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a

Cabré no.	Cabré category	Tomasini category	Tomasini no.	Barral category	Cabré weight	Cabré fineness	Analysis
42	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2	417	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.14	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
43	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2	433	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.38	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
44	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2	423	Légende de Justin II? déformée	0.86	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
45	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2a	437	Légendes de Léovigilde deux fois	1.45	Oro de ley	App. 3.3c
46	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2	431	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.44	Oro bajo	App. 3.3a
47	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2	428	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.47	Oro bajo	App. 3.3a
48	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2	424	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.10	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
49	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2	427	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.19	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
50	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2	432	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.44	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
51	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 2	430	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.10	Oro de ley	App. 3.3a
52	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3	458	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.50	Oro de ley	App. 3.4a
53	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3	442	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.50	Oro bajo	App. 3.4a

Cabré no.	Cabré category	Tomasini category	Tomasini no.	Barral category	Cabré weight	Cabré fineness	Analysis
54	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3	443	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.36	Oro bajo	App. 3-4a
55	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3	444	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.18	Oro bajo	App. 3-4a
56	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3a	470	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.35	Oro bajo	App. 3-4c
57	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3a	469	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.50	Oro bajo	App. 3-4c
58	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3a	468	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.37	Oro bajo	App. 3-4c
59	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3	460	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.49	Oro bajo	App. 3-4a
60	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3	457	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.49	Oro de ley	App. 3-4a
61	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3a	466	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.51	Oro bajo	App. 3-4c
62	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3	445	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.48	Oro bajo	App. 3-4a
63	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3	446	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.55	Oro bajo	App. 3-4a
64	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3	447	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.43	Oro bajo	App. 3-4a
65	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3	467	Inclassable visigot?	1.53	Oro bajo	App. 3-4c

Cabré no.	Cabré category	Tomasini category	Tomasini no.	Barral category	Cabré weight	Cabré fineness	Analysis
66	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3a	471	Légende de Justinien? déformée	1.48	Oro bajo	App. 3-4c
67	Justino II, leyendas confusas	JII 3a	472	Légende de Justinien? déformée	1.40	Oro bajo	App. 3-4c
68	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	JII 6	532	Légende déformée et buste à épaulettes	1.35	Oro bajo	App. 3-7
69	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	JII 6	533	Légende déformée et buste à épaulettes	1.49	Oro bajo	App. 3-7
70	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	JII 6	531	Légende déformée et buste à épaulettes	1.40	Oro bajo	App. 3-7
71	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	JII 6	530	Légende déformée et buste à épaulettes	1.38	Oro bajo	App. 3-7
72	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	JII 3a	473	Légende déformée et buste à épaulettes	1.50	Oro bajo	App. 3-4c
73	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	C 5	598	Légende CVRRV et buste à épaulettes	1.12	Oro de ley	App. 3-11
74	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	JII 4a	500	Légende de Justin II? déformée	1.09	Oro de ley	App. 3-5c
75	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	JII 5b	527	Légende déformée et buste à épaulettes	0.89	Oro de ley	App. 3-6d
76	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	C 3	588	Légende CVRRV et buste à épaulettes	1.19	Oro de ley	App. 3-9a
77	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	C 4	595	Légende CVRRV et buste à épaulettes	1.40	Oro bajo	App. 3-10

Cabré no.	Cabré category	Tomasini category	Tomasini no.	Barral category	Cabré weight	Cabré fineness	Analysis
78	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	C 3	585	Légende CVRRV et buste à épaulettes	1.32	Oro de ley	App. 3.9a
79	Primitiva Leovigildiana, leyendas mudas	C 3	587	Légende CVRRV et buste à épaulettes	1.33	Oro de ley	App. 3.9a
80	Primitiva Leovigildiana a nombre de ¿Liuva?	JII 5b	526	Refrappé	1.05	Oro de ley	App. 3.6d
81	Primitiva Leovigildiana a nombre de ¿Liuva?	JII 3a	477	Légendes de Léovigilde deux fois	1.45	Oro de ley	App. 3.4c
82	Primitiva Leovigildiana a nombre de Leovigildo	JII 3a	475	Légendes de Justin II et de Léovigilde	1.44	Oro de ley	App. 3.4c
83	Primitiva Leovigildiana a nombre de Leovigildo	JII 3a	474	Légendes de Léovigilde deux fois	1.51	Oro de ley	App. 3.4c
84	Primitiva Leovigildiana a nombre de Leovigildo	JII 7	539	Légendes de Léovigilde deux fois	1.20	Oro de ley	App. 3.8
85	Primitiva Leovigildiana a nombre de Leovigildo	JII 7	540	Légendes de Léovigilde deux fois	1.15	Oro de ley	App. 3.8
86	Primitiva Leovigildiana a nombre de Leovigildo	JII 4a	497	Légendes de Léovigilde deux fois	1.25	Oro de ley	App. 3.5c

Cabré no.	Cabré category	Tomasini category	Tomasini no.	Barral category	Cabré weight	Cabré fineness	Analysis
87	Primitiva Leovigildiana a nombre de Leovigildo	JII 4	481	Légendes de Léovigilde deux fois	1.49	Oro de ley	App. 3.5a
88	Primitiva Leovigildiana a nombre de Leovigildo	IR	608	Légende Inclitus rex	1.34	Oro de ley	App. 3.1.2a
89	Primitiva Leovigildiana a nombre de Leovigildo	IR	607	Légende Inclitus rex	1.36	Oro de ley	App. 3.1.2a
90	Primitiva Leovigildiana a nombre de Leovigildo	IR	609	Légende Inclitus rex	—	Cobre chapado de oro	—

APPENDIX 3

The tables in this appendix present the weight and fineness measurements for the Zorita hoard along with similar coins from museum and private collections as discussed in the text. Where measurements were taken from prior literature, the source is given, along with the method of analysis (SG = specific gravity; XRF = X-ray fluorescence; PIXE = particle-induced x-ray emission). Two unpublished XRF measurements were carried out by Nummetrica (Barcelona, Spain). Otherwise, all measurements were done using specific gravity by Peter Bartlett (except three coins of the American Numismatic Society collection, measured for Bartlett by Andrew Kurt and David Yoon, and one coin of the British Museum collection, measured for Bartlett by Duncan Hook).

Appendix 3.1a. Group JAN 2, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 20	1.290	14.78	63	0.81	SG	PB	Tom. 267
Zorita 21	1.350	15.27	68	0.92	SG	PB	Tom. 272
Zorita 22	1.039	16.58	80	0.83	SG	PB	Tom. 276
Zorita 23	1.168	16.76	82	0.96	SG	PB	Tom. 275
Zorita 24	1.054	16.66	81	0.85	SG	PB	Tom. 274
Zorita 25	1.264	16.59	80	1.01	SG	PB	Tom. 273
Mean	1.194		75.7	0.90			
Standard deviation	0.13		8.1	0.079			

Appendix 3.1b. Group JAN 2, other examples

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
ANS 2014.45.4	1.402	17.92	91	1.25	SG	PB	Tom. 247, HSA 503
ANS 2014.45.5	1.432	17.18	85	1.22	SG	PB	Tom. 249, HSA 16768
ANS 2014.45.6	1.443	18.44	94	1.36	SG	PB	Tom. 254, HSA 514
ANS 2014.45.7	1.433	18.22	93	1.34	SG	AK	Tom. 256, HSA 515

ANS 2014.45.8	1.447	18.35	94	1.36	SG	PB	Tom. 257, HSA 8117
ANS 2014.45.9	1.434	18.16	93	1.33	SG	PB	Tom. 258, HSA 511
ANS 2014.45.10	1.439	18.31	92	1.32	SG	PB	Tom. 262, HSA 16744
Ashmolean	1.355	—	92	1.25	XRF	Metcalf & Schweizer O.162	Tom. 248
Ashmolean	1.340	—	94	1.26	XRF	Metcalf & Schweizer O.163	Tom. 261
Fitzwilliam	1.280	18.66	96	1.23	SG	Grierson & Black- burn, <i>MEC</i> 1.194	Tom. 253
Fitzwilliam	1.260	17.91	90	1.13	SG	Grierson & Black- burn, <i>MEC</i> 1.195	
Mean	1.388		92.2	1.277			
Standard deviation	0.068		2.9	0.071			

Appendix 3.1c. Group JAN 2b, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 26	1.275	14.906	64	0.82	SG	PB	Tom. 290

Appendix 3.2a. Group JAN 5, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 15	1.379	14.55	60	0.83	SG	PB	Tom. 347
Zorita 17	1.009	16.57	80	0.81	SG	PB	Tom. 346
Zorita 18	0.988	17.46	87	0.86	SG	PB	Tom. 353
Zorita 29	1.066	16.32	78	0.83	SG	PB	Tom. 354
Mean	1.111		76.3	0.832			
Standard deviation	0.18		11.5	0.022			

Appendix 3.2b. Group JAN 5, other examples

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
ANS 2014.45.22	1.350	17.53	88	1.19	SG	DY	Tom. 344, HSA 16786
ANS 2014.45.23	1.419	17.97	91	1.29	SG	PB	Tom. 345, HSA 502
ANS 2014.45.24	0.913	17.48	87	0.79	SG	PB	Tom. 349, HSA 510
ANS 2014.45.25	1.225	17.78	89	1.09	SG	PB	Tom. 350, HSA 505
ANS 2014.45.26	1.012	17.53	88	0.89	SG	PB	Tom. 351, HSA 506
ANS 2014.45.27	1.411	18.23	93	1.31	SG	PB	Tom. 357, HSA 10619
ANS 2014.45.28	1.411	16.03	75	1.06	SG	PB	Tom. 358, HSA 16733
GNC 9851	1.385	18.29	93	1.29	SG	PB	Amorós 6
GNC 9856	1.432	17.96	91	1.30	SG	PB	Tom. 360, Amorós 7
Mean	1.284		88.4	1.135			
Standard deviation	0.22		5.96	0.021			

Appendix 3.3a. Group III 2, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 27	1.208	16.71	81	0.98	SG	PB	Tom. 418
Zorita 28	1.144	16.90	83	0.95	SG	PB	Tom. 421
Zorita 30	1.091	16.02	75	0.82	SG	PB	Tom. 419
Zorita 31	1.035	16.53	80	0.83	SG	PB	Tom. 413
Zorita 32	1.425	14.67	62	0.88	SG	PB	Tom. 429
Zorita 37	1.137	16.46	79	0.90	SG	PB	Tom. 412
Zorita 38	0.901	16.97	83	0.75	SG	PB	Tom. 420
Zorita 40	1.022	16.26	77	0.79	SG	PB	Tom. 426
Zorita 41	1.256	17.39	87	1.09	SG	PB	Tom. 425
Zorita 42	1.077	17.07	84	0.90	SG	PB	Tom. 417
Zorita 43	1.321	17.27	86	1.14	SG	PB	Tom. 433
Zorita 44	0.766	16.32	78	0.60	SG	PB	Tom. 423
Zorita 46	1.379	13.72	51	0.70	SG	PB	Tom. 431
Zorita 47	1.395	13.39	47	0.66	SG	PB	Tom. 428
Zorita 48	1.008	18.14	92	0.93	SG	PB	Tom. 424
Zorita 49	1.124	15.55	71	0.80	SG	PB	Tom. 427
Zorita 50	1.394	15.75	73	1.02	SG	PB	Tom. 432
Zorita 51	1.024	17.54	88	0.90	SG	PB	Tom. 430
Mean	1.150		76.5	0.87			
Standard deviation	0.184		12.20	0.14			

Appendix 3.3b. Group III 2, other examples

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
GNC 9848	1.156	16.36	78	0.90	SG	PB	Tom. 416, Amorós 9
GNC 9853	1.370	18.44	94	1.29	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	Tom. 437, Amorós 18
Mean	1.263		86.1	1.10			

Standard deviation not meaningful due to small sample.

Appendix 3.3c. Group JII 2a, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 9	1.039	15.55	71	0.74	SG	PB	Tom. 435
Zorita 12	1.190	16.32	78	0.93	SG	PB	Tom. 436
Zorita 45	1.387	15.05	66	0.92	SG	PB	Tom. 437
Mean	1.205		71.7	0.86			
Standard deviation	0.175		6.03	0.107			

Appendix 3.3d. Group JII 2b, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 8	1.360	14.00	54	0.73	SG	PB	Tom. 440
Zorita 10	1.418	14.72	62	0.88	SG	PB	Tom. 439
Zorita 11	1.416	13.67	50	0.71	SG	PB	Tom. 438
Mean	1.398		55.3	0.77			
Standard deviation	0.033		6.11	0.093			

Appendix 3.4a. Group JII 3, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 13	0.966	15.95	74	0.71	SG	PB	Tom. 449
Zorita 14	1.424	15.03	65	0.93	SG	PB	Tom. 454
Zorita 16	1.391	13.59	49	0.68	SG	PB	Tom. 441
Zorita 33	1.337	13.33	45	0.60	SG	PB	Tom. 462
Zorita 34	1.409	14.36	58	0.82	SG	PB	Tom. 461
Zorita 35	1.341	13.35	48	0.64	SG	PB	Tom. 463
Zorita 36	1.353	13.26	44	0.60	SG	PB	Tom. 459
Zorita 52	1.437	13.63	49	0.70	SG	PB	Tom. 458
Zorita 53	1.424	13.55	48	0.68	SG	PB	Tom. 442
Zorita 54	1.292	13.27	45	0.58	SG	PB	Tom. 443
Zorita 55	1.104	13.48	47	0.52	SG	PB	Tom. 444
Zorita 59	1.420	13.26	44	0.62	SG	PB	Tom. 460
Zorita 60	1.421	14.03	55	0.78	SG	PB	Tom. 457
Zorita 62	1.409	13.60	49	0.69	SG	PB	Tom. 445

Zorita 63	1.486	13.07	42	0.62	SG	PB	Tom. 446
Zorita 64	1.377	13.45	47	0.65	SG	PB	Tom. 447
Mean	1.349		50.6	0.68			
Standard deviation	0.134		8.56	0.100			

Appendix 3.4b. Group JII 3, other examples

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
ANS 1956.25.8	1.090	18.30	93	1.01	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 453
Ashmolean	1.370	—	94	1.29	XRF	Metcalf & Schweizer O.169	Tom. 452
PB	1.289	18.13	93	1.20	SG	PB	Tom. 450
Mean	1.250		93.3	1.17			
Standard deviation	0.144		0.577	0.14			

Appendix 3.4c. Group JII 3a, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 39	1.401	14.84	63	0.88	SG	PB	Tom. 476
Zorita 56	1.268	14.80	63	0.80	SG	PB	Tom. 471
Zorita 57	1.442	14.84	63	0.91	SG	PB	Tom. 469
Zorita 58	1.309	14.04	55	0.72	SG	PB	Tom. 468
Zorita 61	1.437	13.71	51	0.73	SG	PB	Tom. 466
Zorita 65	1.473	14.13	56	0.82	SG	PB	Tom. 467
Zorita 66	1.405	14.16	56	0.79	SG	PB	Tom. 471
Zorita 67	1.341	13.92	53	0.71	SG	PB	Tom. 472
Zorita 72	1.431	14.25	57	0.82	SG	PB	Tom. 473
Zorita 81	1.397	14.52	60	0.84	SG	PB	Tom. 477
Zorita 82	1.408	15.10	66	0.93	SG	PB	Tom. 475
Zorita 83	1.446	16.57	80	1.16	SG	PB	Tom. 474
Mean	1.397		60.3	0.84			
Standard deviation	0.061		7.74	0.123			

Appendix 3.5a. Group JII 4, meaningless legends

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
ANS 2014.45.42	1.400	18.20	93	1.30	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 479, HSA 499
Fitzwilliam	1.430	18.19	93	1.33	SG	Grierson & Blackburn, <i>MEC</i> 1.203	Tom. 484
PB 17B	1.333	17.69	89	1.19	SG	PB	
RWH	1.340	—	92	1.23	XRF	Nummetrica	
MNA 17	1.241	—	96	1.20	PIXE	Marques, <i>Ensaio</i> s 25	
Zorita 87	1.431	17.64	89	1.27	SG	PB	Tom. 481
Mean	1.363		92.0	1.25			
Standard deviation	0.073		2.59	0.056			

Appendix 3.5b. Group JII 4, Leovigild legends

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
ANS 2015.48.1	1.310	15.70	72	0.94	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 486, HSA 15990
PB 17A	1.269	16.40	78.5	1.00	SG	Bartlett et al., “Spania”	
MNP 23	1.234	—	87	—*	PIXE	Marques, <i>Ensaio</i> s 1	
Mean	1.271		75	0.97			

* Surface enrichment likely to make this coin not comparable. Standard deviation not meaningful due to small sample when this coin is excluded.

Appendix 3.5c. Group JII 4a, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 74	1.007	14.49	60	0.60			Tom. 500
Zorita 86	1.177	16.16	76	0.89			Tom. 497
Mean	1.092		68	0.75			

Standard deviation not meaningful due to small sample.

Appendix 3.6a. Group JII 5, type I

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
ANS 2015.45.44	1.490	18.10	91.8	1.37	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 502, HSA 16665
Fitzwilliam	1.470	18.67	96	1.41	SG	Grierson & Blackburn, <i>MEC</i> 1.205	Tom. 503
GNC 9864	1.461	18.86	97.1	1.42	SG	PB	Tom. 504
Madrid 106571	1.434	18.51	95.0	1.36	SG	PB	
private coll.	1.409	—	97.3	1.37	PIXE	Marques, <i>Ensaïos</i> 26	
UBP 13	1.474	—	97.1	1.43	PIXE	Metcalfe et al. 11	
MHySyL 216	1.316*	18.94	97.5	1.28	SG	PB	
Mean	1.456		96.0	1.398			
Standard deviation	0.030		2.04	0.05			

* Coin modified for use as jewelry; weight not used in statistics.

Appendix 3.6b. Group JII 5, type II

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
ANS 2014.45.45	1.180	16.90	83	0.98	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 516, HSA 500
Ashmolean	1.492	—	93	1.39	XRF	Metcalfe & Schweizer, O.170	Tom. 515
UBP 14	1.473	—	95	1.40	PIXE	Metcalfe et al., 12	
Barcelona	1.492	18.61	95	1.42	SG	PB	Tom. 510
FAJO 5	1.452	18.39	94	1.36	SG	PB	
FAJO 7	1.467	18.57	95	1.39	SG	PB	
FAJO 11	1.486	18.88	97	1.44	SG	PB	
GC	1.498	18.26	93	1.39	SG	PB	
Madrid 105318	1.310	17.72	89	1.17	SG	PB	

Madrid 1972/75/18	1.472	17.81	90	1.33	SG	PB
Madrid 1973/24/5244	1.481	18.39	94	1.39	SG	PB
Madrid 100441	1.491	17.82	90	1.34	SG	PB
Madrid 106570	1.502	18.18	92	1.38	SG	PB
Mean	1.468		93.1	1.367		
Standard deviation	0.094		3.72	0.013		

Appendix 3.6c. Group JII 5, type III

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
PB 18	1.29	17.51	87.6	1.13	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	
Fitzwilliam	1.30	17.37	86	1.12	SG	Grierson & Blackburn, <i>MEC</i> 1.209	
Madrid 105318	1.31	17.72	89	1.17	SG	PB	
Madrid Cores 15	1.29	17.71	89	1.15	SG	PB	
Pliego 50, lot 259	1.30	17.30	86	1.12	SG	PB	
Yndias 1238	1.47	17.35	86.4	1.27	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	
Mean	1.33		87.3	1.16			
Standard deviation	0.07		1.42	0.058			

Appendix 3.6d. Group JII 5b, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 75	0.804	13.05	42	0.34	SG	PB	Tom. 527
Zorita 80	0.966	15.88	74	0.71	SG	PB	Tom. 526
Mean	0.885		58	0.525			

Standard deviation not meaningful due to small sample.

Appendix 3.7. Group JII 6, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 19	1.098	16.71	81	0.89	SG	PB	Tom. 529
Zorita 68	1.278	14.92	64	0.82	SG	PB	Tom. 532
Zorita 69	1.423	14.52	60	0.85	SG	PB	Tom. 533
Zorita 70	1.360	14.23	57	0.78	SG	PB	Tom. 531
Zorita 71	1.408	14.18	56	0.79	SG	PB	Tom. 530
Mean	1.313		63.6	0.826			
Standard deviation	0.133		10.2	0.045			

Appendix 3.8. Group JII 7, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 84	1.074	15.35	69	0.74	SG	PB	Tom. 539
Zorita 85	1.140	15.32	68	0.78	SG	PB	Tom. 540
Mean	1.107		68.5	0.76			

Standard deviation not meaningful due to small sample.

Appendix 3.9a. Group C 3, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 76	1.115	17.69	89	0.99	SG	PB	Tom. 588
Zorita 78	1.245	17.53	88	1.10	SG	PB	Tom. 585
Zorita 79	1.250	16.89	83	1.04	SG	PB	Tom. 587
Mean	1.203		86.7	1.042			
Standard deviation	0.077		3.2	0.052			

Appendix 3.9b. Group C 3, other examples

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
ANS 2014.45.54	1.270	17.90	91	1.15	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 569, HSA 15981
GNC 9852	1.330	18.40	94	1.25	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	Tom. 570, Amorós 14
PB 13	1.320	18.60	95	1.26	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	
GNC 9855	1.410	18.64	96	1.35	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	Tom. 571, Amorós 15
GNC 9854	1.020	18.08	92	0.94	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	Tom. 572, Amorós 16
Fitzwilliam	1.400	18.59	95	1.33	SG	Grierson & Blackburn, <i>MEC</i> 1.207	Tom. 573
ANS 2014.45.55	1.280	17.60	88	1.13	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 574, HSA 497
ANS 2014.45.56	1.280	18.40	94	1.20	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 575, HSA 16756
ANS 1957.28.1	1.270	18.40	94	1.19	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 577
ANS 2014.45.57	1.350	17.00	84	1.13	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 578, HSA 501
PB 14	1.240	17.90	92	1.14	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	
Yndias 1234	1.260	17.49	87	1.10	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	
UBP 24	1.395	—	96	1.34	XRF	Metcalf et al., 21	
PB 15	1.26	18.10	92	1.16	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	
Private coll.	1.27	—	96	1.22	PIXE	Marques, <i>Ensaïos</i> 30	
Yndias 1235	1.35	18.01	91	1.23	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	
Yndias 1236	1.35	17.85	90	1.22	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	
Pliego 127	1.35	—	92	1.24	XRF	Nummet- rica	

PB 15-B	1.023	16.85	82	0.84	SG	PB	
Private coll.	1.28	—	93	1.18	PIXE	Marques, <i>Ensaio</i> s 31	
Private coll.	1.34	—	89	1.19	PIXE	Marques, <i>Ensaio</i> s 32	
Mean	1.288		91.0	1.18			
Standard deviation	0.102		3.79	0.119			

Appendix 3.10. Group C 4, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 77	1.318	14.70	62	0.82	SG	PB	Tom. 595

Appendix 3.11. Group C 5, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 73	1.035	18.18	92	0.95	SG	PB	Tom. 598

Appendix 3.12a. Group IR, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 88	1.262	15.83	73	0.92	SG	PB	Tom. 608
Zorita 89	1.288	16.21	77	0.99	SG	PB	Tom. 607
Mean	1.275		75	0.96	SG	PB	

Standard deviation not meaningful due to small sample.

Appendix 3.12b. Group IR, other examples

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
ANS 2015.48.4	1.29	15.50	70	0.90	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 619, HSA 16002
ANS 2015.48.3	1.31	15.60	70	0.92	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 620, HSA 16003
ANS 2015.48.5	1.31	15.80	73	0.96	SG	L. Olson	Tom. 621, HSA 16781
PB 19	1.27	17.30	86	1.09	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	

PB 20	1.31	15.90	74	0.97	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	
Cores	1.28	16.70	81	1.04	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	Pliego, <i>Moneda visigoda</i> , 11(a)4
GNC 9877	1.32	16.10	76	1.00	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	
GNC 9868	1.33	16.40	78	1.04	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	
J. Vico 136, lot 633	1.51	16.18	77	1.16	SG	PB	
Mean	1.33		76.1	1.01			
Standard deviation	0.072		5.18	0.083			

Appendix 3.12c. Group H 2

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Paris 13	1.36	16.30	78	1.06	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	Pliego, <i>Moneda visigoda</i> , 62(a)1
Cores	1.30	16.90	83	1.08	SG	Bartlett et al., "Spania"	Pliego, <i>Moneda visigoda</i> , 62(c)1
NG 7, lot 1244	1.297	16.79	82	1.06	SG	PB	
JAH May 2015, lot 219	1.245	16.85	82	1.02	SG	PB	
Mean	1.30		81.2	1.05			
Standard deviation	0.047		2.4	0.025			

Appendix 3.12d. Group H 3

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
BM 1863, 1110.1	1.270		87	1.10	SG	DH	Pliego, <i>Moneda visigoda</i> , 61(b) ₁

Appendix 3.13a. Byzantine Spania, Justin II

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
DO BZC 2009.05	1.38	17.70	89	1.22	SG	PB	
J. Dwyer	1.37	17.61	88	1.20	SG	PB	
GNC 9857	1.47	17.23	85	1.24	SG	PB	Amorós 3
Zorita 5	1.101	17.04	84	0.93	SG	PB	
Mean	1.330		86.5	1.148			
Standard deviation	0.159		2.4	0.146			

Appendix 3.13b. Suevic Latina Munita

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 7	0.925	14.18	56	0.52	SG	PB	
ANS 2014.44.8	1.115*	13.43	46	0.52	SG	DY	HSA 16783
Fitzwilliam	1.22**	14.40	59	0.72	SG	Grierson & Blackburn, <i>MEC</i> 1.293	
Mean	1.087		54	0.59			
Standard deviation	0.150		6.8	0.115			

* Coin is broken; estimated intact weight around 1.15 g, giving an intrinsic value of 0.53 g.

** Coin is broken; estimated intact weight around 1.24 g, giving an intrinsic value of 0.73 g.

Appendix 3.13c. Suevic Latina Emeri Munita

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Câmara Municipal do Porto	1.268	—	86		PIXE	Cabral & Metcalf, <i>Moeda sueva</i> , pl. 17 no. 1	
Private coll.	1.205	15.52	70	0.85	SG	PB	
Private coll.	1.172	14.97	65	0.76	SG	PB	
Mean (SG only)	1.215	15.25	67.5	0.80			

Appendix 3.13d. Tomasini Unsorted group, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 6	1.394	16.45	79	1.10	SG	PB	Tom. 657

Appendix 3.13e. Merovingian-type coins, Zorita hoard

	Weight (g)	SG	Fineness (%)	Intrinsic value (g)	Method	Source	Cross-ref.
Zorita 1	1.440	15.18	67	0.96	SG	PB	
Zorita 2	1.433	15.15	67	0.96	SG	PB	
Zorita 3	1.475	14.69	62	0.91	SG	PB	
Zorita 4	1.398	14.99	65	0.91	SG	PB	
Mean	1.437		65.3	0.935			
Standard deviation	0.032		2.36	0.029			

Jl 1

1

JAN 3

2

JAN 2/JAN 8

3

4

5

43

JAN 5

9

10

JII 2

11

12

13

14

15

16

JII 3

17

18

19

20

JII 4

21

22

JII 5

23

24

25

26

27

28

29

